

DPP4EU Conference

Albert Borschette Conference Center, rue Froissart, 36, Brussels

June 16 – June 18, 2025

ABSTRACT BOOKLET

Programme Overview

16 June 2025 — Opening Day

Time	Activity / Session
13:00–14:00	Registration
14:00–14:10	Opening and Welcome <i>Chairs:Carolynn Bernier, Natalia Konchakova, Kostas Chatziioannou</i>

Session 1: Regulations and Standards. *Chair: Peter Klein, Carolynn Bernier*

Time	Activity / Session
14:10–14:30	DPP implementation status, Alexandru Ion, DG GROW, European Commission
14:30–14:45	Standardisation for DPP by CEN/CENELEC JTC-24
14:45–15:30	Session 1 – Part 1
15:30–15:50	Coffee Break and Networking
15:50–16:50	Session 1 – Part 2
16:50–17:10	Coffee Break

Session 2: DPPs — Barriers, Challenges, and Opportunities. *Chair: Salim Belouettar, Natalia Konchakova*

Time	Activity / Session
17:10–18:10	Session 2 - Part 1
18:10–18:30	Poster pitch
18:30–19:30	Networking and Poster Session

17 June 2025 — Implementation and Practice

Session 2: DPPs — Barriers, Challenges, and Opportunities. *Chair: Salim Belouettar, Natalia Konchakova*

Time	Activity / Session
09:00–09:20	DG ENVI's perspectives on the implementation of DPPs, Wojtek Sitarz, DG ENVI, European Commission
09:20–10:20	Session 2 - Part 2
10:20–10:40	Coffee Break and Networking

Session 3: Technical Requirements for DPPs. *Chairs: Natalia Konchakova, Peter Klein.*

Time	Activity / Session
10:40–11:00	The European Business Wallet, Alina Radu, DG CONNECT, European Commission
11:00–12:00	Session 3 – Part 1
12:00–12:20	Coffee Break and Networking
12:20–13:20	Session 3 – Part 2
13:20–14:20	Lunch Break

Session 4: Emerging Technologies for DPPs. *Chairs:Carolynn Bernier, Kostas Chatziioannou.*

Time	Activity / Session
14:40–15:40	Session 4
15:40–16:00	<i>Coffee Break and Networking</i>

Session 5: Bridging Sustainable by Design (SSbD) through DPPs. *Chair: Natalia Konchakova, Peter Klein*

Time	Activity / Session
16:00–16:20	A framework for Safe and Sustainable by design chemicals and materials, Garbine Guiu Etxeberria, DG RTD, European Commission
16:20–17:20	Session 5 - Part 1
17:20–17:40	<i>Coffee Break and Networking</i>
17:40–18:10	Session 5 - Part 2
18:10–19:30	<i>Wrap up of the Day 2 and Cocktail event</i>

18 June 2025 — Final Day and Forward Look

Session 6: Enabling Industrial and Manufacturing Data Ecosystems. *Chair: Kostas Chatziioannou, Stella Georgali*

Time	Activity / Session
09:00–09:20	The value for industry of the DPP, Ilias Iakovidis, DG CONNECT, European Commission
09:20–10:20	Session 6 – Part 1
10:20–10:40	<i>Coffee Break and Networking</i>
10:40–12:00	Session 6 – Part 2
12:00–13:00	<i>Lunch Break</i>

Session 7: From Research to Commercial Valorisation. *Chair: Franz Pirker, Stella Georgali*

Time	Activity / Session
13:00–13:20	Materials Commons for Europe - challenges and strategy, Wide Hogenhout, DG RTD, European Commission
13:20–14:20	Session 7
14:20–14:40	<i>Coffee Break and Networking</i>

Final Session: Panel Discussion on the Future of DPPs. *Chair: Natalia Konchakova*

Time	Activity / Session
14:40–15:25	The DPP in 2050: Panel Discussion on the Future of DPPs Moderator: Natalia Konchakova. Panelists: Fani Tsirantonaki (HaDEA, European Commission) Thomas Ebert (DG CONNECT, European Commission) Martin Policar (DG RTD, European Commission) Eva-Kathrin Schillinger (IAM-I, IAM4EU Partnership) Eugenio Alessandro Canepa (Piacenza 1733, industry) Peter Klein (Fraunhofer ITWM, RTO)

Open microphone session *Chair: Carolyn Bernier*

Time	Activity / Session
15:25–16:15	Open microphone session: Future collaborations discussion

Time	Activity / Session
16:15–16:30	Discussion and Closing Remarks Sophia Fantechi, DG RTD, European Commission <i>Natalia Konchakova, Carolyn Bernier, Kostas Chatziioannou</i>

Table of Contents

Introduction	8
Session 1: Regulations & Standards. Chairs: Peter Klein, Carolynn Bernier	10
Digital Product Passport for a Low-Carbon, Circular Construction Industry: The RECONSTRUCT Project Jose Lucas	11
Digital Product Passport - Empowering Sustainable Products and Consumer Confidence through Verifiable Credentials and EU Business Wallet Florin Coptil	12
BASE: Battery Passport for Resilient Supply Chains and Circular Economy Implementation. Shahin Jamali	13
Circular Intelligence - a decentralized platform for life-cycle data sharing Rembrandt Koppelaar	14
Harmonizing Standards for the Digital Product Passport: The CLC-SDPP Project Marvin Boell	15
BatteryPass-Ready: Enabling Digital Product Passports for Batteries in the EU Regulatory Landscape Johannes Simböck	15
CIRPASS-2: Towards cross-pilot interoperability Emrah Danisman	17
Session 2 - Part 1: DPPs Barriers, Challenges and Oportunities. Chairs: Salim Belouettar, Natalia Konchakova	18
Digitalization and Circular Economy Enablement for the Fluid Power Industry Martin Hankel	19
Digital Product Passport for Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries and Carbon Felt Electrodes: Addressing Technical Challenges and Regulatory Compliance Maria Bashir	20
Digital Battery Passport for Maritime Applications to Support Circular Economy Werner Rom	21
Circular & Sustainable Textiles & Clothing (CISUTAC) – A Step Toward a Circular Economy in Textiles Guy Buyle	22
Poster session	23
Provisions for the Inclusion of Safety Data in the Digital Materials Passports Thomas Exner	23
Safety Testing of Emerging Products: The iCare Project and Its Contribution to Product Lifecycle Information Elise Morel	24
PSS-Pass: Digital Product Service System Passport for Circularity in Manufacturing. Kevin Nagorny	25
champl4.0ns - Enabling Intelligent and Sovereign Use of Data in Production. Arko Steinwender	26
PASSAT - Supporting the Implementation of Digital Product Passports (DPPs). Arko Steinwender	27
Centre of Excellence for Digital Product Passports - NL Sjoerd Rongen	28
Preparing SMEs for Digital Product Passports: A Regional Knowledge Hub in Halland Maria Hammar	29
Enhancing DPP implementation trough a digital Quality Infrastructure: Data Spaces and beyond. Anna Maria Elert	30
The DPP as a facilitator of high granularity information to industries, territories and regions Kostas Chatziioannou	31

Session 2 - Part 2: DPPs Barriers, Challenges and Oportunities. Chairs: Salim Belouettar, Natalia Konchakova	32
CE-RISE: Enabling Circularity Through Digital Product Passports and Open Data Systems.	
Miguel Las Heras Hernández	32
NEO-CYCLE - Sustainable Upcycling of Spent NdFeB Magnets and the Integration of Digital Product Passports (DPPs).	
Arko Steinwender	33
Governance Framework for Digital Product Passports in the Furniture Sector – The R-Evolve Project.	
Holger Berg	34
DYMAN DPPs and DBLs for Cooling Technologies in Data Centres: Enabling Interoperable, Lifecycle-Based Digital Information Exchange	
Emre Yontem	35
Session 3: Technical Requirements and Implementation of DPPs. Chairs: Peter Klein, Natalia Konchakova	36
Innovation by Design – supporting Digital Maturity of Advanced Materials Communities	
Natalia Konchakova	36
Accelerating the Digital and Green Transitions through Semantic Interoperability: The Onto-DESIDE Project and Digital Product Passports.	
Huanyu Li	37
Modular Architecture for Digital Product Passports (DPPs) for Critical Raw Materials: Enhancing Sustainability, Compliance, and Circularity	
Doruk Sahinel	38
Leveraging AI for Circular Value Chains: The ENCIRCLE Project and Blockchain-Enabled Digital Product Passports.	
Nikolaos Dimitriou	39
Enabling Circular Economy with Digital Product Passports: The DaCapo Project	
Kristiina Valtanen	40
Advancing Sustainable Industries through Data-Driven Digital Product Passport Solutions: TVS' Pioneering Role in European Innovation	
Farhad Arifin	41
Battery Digital Product Passport Demonstrator in Horizon Europe BatWoMan.	
Margit Kranner	42
RecAI Digital Product Passport: Enhancing Traceability and Transparency in the Aluminum Supply Chain	
Symeonidis Panagiotis	43
Session 4: Emerging Technologies for DPPs. Chairs: Carolyn Bernier, Kostas Chatziioannou	44
TRICK: Product Data Traceability from Cradle to Cradle by Blockchains Interoperability and Sustainability Service Marketplace	
Alessandro Canepa	44
AIDEAS - DPPs for manufacturing machines	
Georgia Kougka	45
DigInTraCE: Novel transparent and interoperable Decentralised Traceability platform via the development of Dynamically updated Digital Product Passport schemes that support certification and quality validation in industrial set-ups	
Lefteris Gounaridis	46
Development of the Digital Bio-product Passport for Environmental Impact Assessment in Bio-based Value Chains	
Milenko Tomic	47
Session 5: Bridging Sustainable by Design (SSbD) Principles, Innovation and Manufacturing through DPPs. Chairs: Natalia Konchakova, Peter Klein	48
Bridging the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) with Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)	
Lya G. Soeteman-Hernandez	49

From conceptualizing a full material life cycle to a standards-based data model	
Raul Carlsson	50
Enabling Semantic Interoperability in Materials Science: The MaterialDigital Initiative	
Jörg Schaarschmidt	51
Standardizing Composite Material Test Data for Digital Product Passports in Aerospace and Wind Energy Sectors	
Julian de Marchi	52
Digital Material and Product Passports: Advancing SSbD in the PINK Project	
Thomas Exner	53
REMHUB project: safe and sustainable REE by design framework	
Damijan Miljavec	54
Session 6: Enabling industrial and manufacturing data ecosystems. Chairs: Kostas Chatziioannou, Stella Georgali	55
SMARTChain: Digital Material and Product Passports driving circularity, innovation, and quality in the steel supply chain	
Stella Georgali	55
DigiPass CSA: Coordinating the European DPP Ecosystem.	
Salim Belouettar	56
The Digital Product Information Systems (DPIS) Global Framework: Harmonizing Sustainability Data for a Global Impact	
Ana Gabriela Vergara	57
AI-driven Decision Making in Material Selection for Sustainability using Digital Product Passports	
Maddalena Rostagno	58
How to Create, Exchange, and Use DPPs in Industrial & Manufacturing Data Ecosystems	
Christoph Attila Kun	59
Digital Product Passports and Circular Manufacturing Data Spaces: Two Sides of the Same Twin Transition Coin.	
Cinzia Rubattino	60
SENECA: Advancing Sustainability through Digital Product Passports and Data Spaces	
Carlos Méndez	61
PASSAT - Product Access and Secure Sharing by Automated Trust	
Rigo Wenning	62
What does a chemical DPP contribute to building a sustainable circular economy?	
Adrian von Muehlenen	63
Session 7: From research to commercial valorization. Chairs: Franz Pirker, Stella Georgali	64
A large scale DPP initiative in France and in Europe	
Xavier Lantoinette	64
TRACE4EU – Digital Product Passports Leveraging the European Blockchain Service Infrastructure.	
Steffen Schwalm	65
Proposal for a Cross-Project Working Group on DPP Use Cases in Electronics	
Bernhard Bergmair	66
Business Models across Safe and Sustainable by Design-, Open Innovation Test Beds and Digital Materials and Product Passport initiatives	
Franz Pirker	67
Final Session: Panel Discussion on the Future of DPPs. Chair: Natalia Konchakova	68
Open Microphone Session: Future collaboration discussion. Chair:Carolynn Bernier	68

Introduction

Preamble:

The **DPP4EU-25 conference** had been held on June 16-18, 2025 in Brussels (<https://digipassforum.eu/>). Predecessor of this event used to be three clustering events on Open-Innovation organized 2022 in Brussels (Belgium), 2023 in Esch-sur-Alzette (Luxembourg) and 2024 in Kaiserslautern (Germany), where digitalization aspects of B2B2B value chain integration had been discussed from an open-innovation facilitation angle.

The follow up DPP4EU-25 conference was initiated, conceptualized and organized by three EU-funded projects: DigiPass CSA, CIRPASS-2 and THESEUS, greatly supported and guided by the European Commission Directorates-General DG-RTD and DG-CNECT, and assisted by the European Commission Health and Digital Executive Agency (HaDEA). In particular, the organization committee of DPP4EU-25 is thankful to **Sophia Fantechi** (DG RTD), **Fani Tsirantonaki** (HaDEA), **Martin Policar** (DG RTD), and **Thomas Ebert** (DG CNECT), for their dedication, support and help.

Moreover, the organization committee would like to thank **all projects** and **authors** who discussed from a multi-disciplinary perspective the DPP development, challenges and possible solutions.

Short Overview:

The DPP4EU-25 was dedicated to **digitalization, Digital Product Passport (DPPs) and management of materials, product information & data** as a tool to support **sustainability**, and **circularity**.

The conference had been designed as a clustering event and as a forum for experts from European-funded initiatives related to DPP developments. Open questions and the exchange of insights regarding DPPs' technical implementation, the role of IT infrastructures, implications for digitalization of manufacturing, correlations with Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) frameworks, and digital business models were discussed in **7 technical sessions**, a **poster session**, a **Panel Discussion** on the "DPP and Material Digitalization Future" and an **Open Microphone** session.

The event addressed topics relevant to multiple European Commission DGs: DG RTD, DG CNECT, DG GROW, and DG ENVI, and representatives from all these DGs actively participated in the conference.

The **technical sessions** were focused on the following aspects:

- Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and other related regulations and their links to Digital Product Passports (DPPs) → **Session 1: Regulations & Standards**.
- DPPs' contributions to circular economy goals such as reuse, recycling, and waste reduction → **Session 2: DPPs Barriers, Challenges and Opportunities**.
- Digital platforms and tools (Large Research Infrastructures, Open Innovation Platforms and Test Beds, Materials Acceleration Platforms, Factories of the Future, and Digital Innovation Hubs) supported the successful implementation of DPPs. → **Session 3: Technical Requirements and Implementation of DPPs**.
- Role of Artificial Intelligence and emerging technologies in the development and optimization of DPPs and materials digitalization systems → **Session 4: Emerging Technologies for DPPs**.
- Digitalization of Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) principles and research-driven methodologies for seamless integration into industrial production and supply chains → **Session 5: Bridging Sustainable by Design Principles, Innovation and Manufacturing through DPPs**.
- Manufacturing process data used to enhance DPPs, including business-to-business (B2B) and business-to-research (B2RTO) data sharing → **Session 6: Enabling industrial and manufacturing data ecosystems**.
- Business potential/value of DPPs as assets in digital platforms, open innovation strategies, and sustainable business models across multiple industries → **Session 7: From research to commercial valorization**.

The **poster** session hosted contributions covering all topics discussed in the technical sessions described above.

Sectors Represented

Over **900 participants** (approximately 100 experts in the meeting room and 800+ online) attended the event for 3 days:

- **Industry:** more than 50% of attendees
- **Academia:** about 20% of participants
- **Civil Society / NGO:** about 20% of participants
- **Government / Public Sector:** about 5% of participants

During the final **Panel Discussion**, the questions presented below were discussed by representatives of the European Commission, Co-Programming partnership, Industry and Academia:

- Martin Policar (DG RTD), Thomas Ebert (DG CNECT), Fani Tsiirantonaki (HaDEA)
- Eva-Kathrin Schillinger (IAM-I/ IAM4EU Partnership)
- Eugenio Alessandro Canepa (Piacenza, TRICK Project)
- Peter Klein (Fraunhofer ITWM, DigiPass CSA)

At the last session of the event, Sophia Fantechi (DG RTD) and Ilias Iakovidis (DG CNECT) provided an overview on the general policy and vision of the future development of materials digitalization, DPP, and the European business wallet.

Impressions from the participants are published on Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/records/17194755>), showing the necessity of a continuation in 2026.

Organization & Scientific Committee:

DigiPass CSA: Natalia Konchakova (Helmholtz Zentrum hereon GmbH, Germany), Salim Belouettar (Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology, Luxembourg), Peter Klein (Fraunhofer Institute for Industrial Mathematics ITWM, Germany), Franz Pirker (AC2T GmbH, Austria), Martin Thomas Horsch (Norwegian University of Life Science, Norway);

CIRPASS-2: Carolynn Bernier (French Atomic Energy and Alternative Energies Commission CEA, France);

THESEUS: Lucyna Lekawska-Andrinopoulou, Kostas Chatziioannou, Stella Georgali (Institute of Communication and Computer System ICCS, Greece).

Acknowledgement: The conference was organized by 3 EU funded projects managed by HaDEA: **DigiPass** CSA is funded by the EC under Horizon Europe GA no. 101138510; the UK partner WIKKI Ltd is supported by UKRI under grant no. 10100819: DigiPass. **CIRPASS-2** is funded by the EC under the Digital Europe Programme GA no. 101158775. **THESEUS** funded by the EC under GA no. 101178059.

Session 1: Regulations & Standards.

Chairs: Peter Klein, Carolynn Bernier

This session provides an overview of the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and other related regulations and their links to Digital Product Passports (DPPs). Key discussions will include the regulatory framework, objectives, and scope of the ESPR, emphasizing how DPPs support sustainability and circularity. Topics include product lifecycle information, environmental impact assessments, standardization efforts, and legal considerations related to data collection, sharing, and compliance.

ID: 101

Time: 14:45

Title: Digital Product Passport for a Low-Carbon, Circular Construction Industry: The RECONSTRUCT Project

Project Reference: RECONSTRUCT (GA 101082265) - Horizon Europe

Jose Lucas

ITeC jlucas@itec.cat

Abstract: In an era defined by urgent climate imperatives, resource scarcity, and increasing regulatory demands, the construction sector stands at a crossroads. As one of the largest consumers of raw materials and a significant contributor to global greenhouse gas emissions, the industry is under pressure to transition toward sustainable, circular, and digital practices. One of the most promising tools in this transformation is the Digital Product Passport (DPP), a structured digital record designed to capture and share comprehensive data on a product's composition, environmental impact, lifecycle performance, and regulatory compliance. This abstract presents the conceptual foundations, technical architecture, and practical applications of the Digital Product Passport developed in the RECONSTRUCT project—a European initiative that aims to create a territorial construction system for a low-carbon, circular built environment. The Digital Product Passport (DPP) developed within RECONSTRUCT emerges from the intersection of regulatory necessity and technological opportunity. Mandated under frameworks such as the EU's Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP), and the European Green Deal, DPPs are positioned as enablers of transparent, circular supply chains. In this context, the RECONSTRUCT DPP is tailored for the construction industry, specifically designed to address the unique challenges of tracking, tracing, and documenting material flows across complex and often fragmented construction value chains. A Digital Product Passport, in its essence, acts as a digital twin of a physical product. It aggregates both static and dynamic data that accompany the product throughout its lifecycle. This includes unique identifiers (for the product, economic operator, and manufacturing facility), performance declarations (e.g., Declaration of Performance and Declaration of Conformity), environmental data (such as carbon footprint and lifecycle assessment results), material composition, and information on reparability, recyclability, and end-of-life management. These components are structured to enable compliance with EU regulations, foster consumer and stakeholder trust, and promote reuse and high-quality recycling.

Technologically, the RECONSTRUCT DPP is built using an XML-based architecture. XML was selected for its hierarchical structure, self-descriptive properties, machine-readability, and broad compatibility with other digital standards used in the construction sector, including ILCD+EPD, smart CE marking systems, and BIM-based data exchange protocols. The document's structure enables interoperability across platforms and aligns with ISO and CEN standards such as EN ISO 23386, 23387, 22057, and the recently developed ISO/FDIS 59040 for circularity data reporting. The RECONSTRUCT DPP includes a modular architecture capable of adapting to different product types used in the project—ranging from alkali-activated cement (AAC) to precast concrete panels and modular TRRC sandwich floor elements. Each product type is associated with a specific regulatory pathway (harmonized standard, European Assessment Document, or mutual recognition), which determines the applicable performance criteria and data requirements. Static components, such as environmental and circularity data, remain consistent across product types, ensuring scalability and replicability of the passport structure.

One of the defining features of the RECONSTRUCT approach is its deep integration with circular economy principles. The DPP explicitly supports circularity by including modules that track recycled content, reusability, refurbishment potential, energy recovery, and disassembly instructions. These data points are not only useful for post-consumer product management but are also essential for design-phase decisions, regulatory assessments, and environmental certifications. The DPP format also supports the principles of Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR), enabling traceability and accountability beyond the point of sale.

Keywords: Digital Product Passport; Construction; Circular Economy; Low-Carbon Materials; Regulatory Compliance Regulatory Framework

ID: 102**Time: 15:00**

Title: Digital Product Passport - Empowering Sustainable Products and Consumer Confidence through Verifiable Credentials and EU Business Wallet

Project Reference: National Project (IDunion) and collaboration with EU-Large Scale Projects (EWC)

Florin Coptil

Robert Bosch GmbH florin.coptil@bosch.com

Abstract: This contribution presents a concept and demonstrator for Digital Product Passport (DPP) system powered by Verifiable Credentials (VCs). Designed for interoperability, scalability and regulatory alignment the solution supports seamless data exchange across diverse stakeholders and product types.

Key features include:

- Data Carrier Agnostic: can be embedded with any data carriers listed in the StandICT.eu 2026 landscape.
- Product Agnostic: Applicable to batch-based, lot-based, and individualized products.
- Seamless Identification: Aligned with eIDAS 2.0, enabling secure authentication of both individuals and organizations.
- Technology Stack Independent: No dedicated app required, ensuring accessibility and low adoption barriers.
- Technology Stack Independent: No dedicated app required, ensuring accessibility and low adoption barriers.
- Lightweight & Semantically Rich: Utilizes VCs with semantic data models to guarantee machine-readability and interoperability.
- Cryptographically Verifiable: Ensures authenticity, integrity and verifiability of data without relying on third parties.
- Trust Infrastructure Integration: Supports linkage to EU Trust Frameworks and Digital Identity Wallets.
- Easy integration with Upstream: Enables collection of attestations directly from supply chain actors, increasing trust and data accuracy.

The solution addresses the needs of a broad range of stakeholders – from raw material suppliers and manufacturers to consumers, recyclers, and regulatory bodies. Through interactive demonstrations, we showcase how a decentralized, trustworthy DPP ecosystem fosters sustainability, transparency and compliance across the product lifecycle.

Overview here: https://idunion.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/0_Video_Grundlagen_DPP.mp4

More information and demo material: <https://idunion.org/piloten/en/sichere-digitale-identitaeten-fuer-produkte/>

Keywords: Digital Product Passport (DPP), Verifiable Credentials (VCs), Trustworthy Data, Interoperability, Scalability, Regulatory Alignment, Data Carrier Agnostic, Product Agnostic, Data Authenticity, Data Integrity, Decentralized Ecosystem, Interactive Demonstrations

ID: 103**Title:** BASE: Battery Passport for Resilient Supply Chains and Circular Economy Implementation**Time: 15:15****Project Reference:** BASE - Grant Agreement No. 101157200; Horizon Europe Programme*Shahin Jamali**Fraunhofer IEG shahin.jamali@ieg.fraunhofer.de*

Abstract: The European Union's forthcoming Battery Regulation mandates the implementation of Digital Battery Passports (DBPs) to enhance sustainability, traceability, and circularity within the battery industry. In response, the BASE (Battery Passport for Resilient Supply Chain and Implementation of Circular Economy) project, funded under Horizon Europe (Grant Agreement No. 101157200), aims to develop and validate a comprehensive DBP ecosystem.

Keywords: Battery Passport, Circular Economy, Data Space, Traceability, Sustainability

BASE focuses on creating an interoperable data space that ensures end-to-end data exchange, among the stakeholders from raw material sourcing to end-of-life management to create, update and maintain DBP across entire battery lifecycle. By leveraging Catena-X standards for data space and Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), the project guarantees secure, authenticate data transfer while ensuring data sovereignty and trust among the stakeholders.

The project employs advanced analytical and AI techniques to estimate key performance and safety indicators, facilitating informed decision-making for extending the life of batteries. Moreover, BASE introduces circularity metrics based on the 4R principles; Reduce, Repair, Reuse, and Recycle; and harmonized Environmental, Social, Governance, and Economic (ESGE) indicators to promote sustainable practices.

To validate the DBP framework, BASE conducts pilot implementations across diverse sectors: automotive (e.g., electric buses by Mercedes-Benz and frugal EVs by Ford Motors), marine (all-electric tugboats by Navtek and Corvus Energy), and stationary energy storage systems (second-life applications by BeePlanet Factory).

The project's technical approach is structured into distinct work packages, each addressing specific facets of the DBP development and implementation. These include implementation of BASE portal and data space, integration of DLT for secure data management, development of AI-driven analytical tools, and establishment of ESGE and circularity indicators. The collaborative efforts across these work packages ensure a holistic and robust DBP solution.

By aligning technological innovation with regulatory requirements, BASE exemplifies how digital transformation can drive sustainability and resilience in the battery value chain. The project's outcomes are poised to inform policy development and industry standards, contributing to the EU's vision of a circular and competitive battery ecosystem.

ID: 104
Time: 15:50

Title: Circular Intelligence - a decentralized platform for life-cycle data sharing

Project Reference: CIRCthread

Rembrandt Koppelaar

Ecowise rembrandt.koppelaar@eco-wise.co.uk

Keywords:

Abstract: CIRCthread project's objective is to interconnect the information along the life of a product, from concept to retirement, so that it can be easily accessed and shared, allowing stakeholders to make decisions at all stages to shift to a circular economy.

The project developed the de-centralised Circular Intelligence platform to store and manage the product information along with multiple software services that support the circular operations and decision making. The overarching aim is to deliver a marketplace software platform, where individual products will become traceable across their extended life cycle supported with their Digital Identities and Product Passports, with links to information in a public accessible "catalogue". The provided services include Life Cycle Impact Assessment, End of life recommendation services, product tracing and surveying tools.

Emerging circular applications data spaces can offer substantial benefits for key players across supply chains. A data space is an IT environment where different economic operators, which can include competitors, are brought together to achieve shared data sharing objectives. However, the successful deployment of circular data spaces requires robust governance, with clear rules for data ownership, usage policies, security, and privacy protections, while accommodating the diverse needs of small and medium enterprises (SMEs), large manufacturers, and other stakeholders.

The circular economy monitoring framework needs to rely on the best possible data while reducing reliance on assumptions and secondary data. The DPP has the potential to improve Eurostat datasets by providing detailed, product specific materials information that can be updated on an on-going quarterly basis. CIRCthread project has invested on the proposition that the DPP can be used to collect primary data on the material footprint of products for all products placed on the market, playing a crucial role in delivering highly accurate precise and up-to-date material flow datasets. Importantly, the automated exchange requirements of DPPs can also allow this to be delivered on a low cost and up-to-date basis, through direct DPP IT integrations with a bottom-up EU wide material flow accounts system. This will allow over time shifting from existing extrapolations-based input-output material flow accounting to direct calculations of materials placed in products on the EU market.

The project partners have delivered 3 widescale implementations of the decentralised Circular Intelligence Platform in Spain, Italy and Slovenia, supported by DPPs, covering all life cycle stages of the selected house appliances value chains. The solution provided multiple benefits on the circularity of the complete system, including: Enhanced design decisions, collection of consumer insights and feedback, support to disassembly stages, monitoring and reutilisation of CRM and as a whole management and reporting of product life cycle information.

The project champions that besides European targets, the DPP could also support companies in setting their own circularity targets, with a focus on those that can be trusted by the consumers. By mandating that companies collect data upstream to calculate their material footprint, they would ensure that companies are aware of the environmental impact of their inflows, thus revolutionising the supply chain in a transparent fashion.

ID: 105**Time: 16:05****Title:** Harmonizing Standards for the Digital Product Passport: The CLC-SDPP Project**Project References:** 101182727 — CLC-SDPP European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA)*Marvin Böll**VDE e.V. DKE marvin.boell@vde.com*

Abstract: Due to the adoption of the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) in 2025, and the adoption of the Digital Product Passport (DPP) for the first products in 2027, a timely delivery of harmonized standards poses a challenge to the European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (CENELEC). The challenge is reinforced given the broad spectrum of areas of standardization that CENELEC must cover, such as the interoperability IT architectures as well as information included in the DPP (e.g., raw materials, product carbon footprint, etc.) classified by delegated acts. There is the risk, that the Technical Committees (TC), developing the product specific standards, might not be sufficiently prepared for a rollout of the DPP.

Keywords: Digital Product Passport (DPP), Ecodesign Regulation, Standardization, Interoperability, Product Carbon Footprint

In support of the coordination and the alignment of the European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs) on IT-standards and product relevant standards relevant for the DPP, the European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA) started the “CLC-SDPP-Project”. The project consortium consists of the National Standardization Bodies DKE, CEI, AFNOR. The project start was 01.01.2024 with a runtime of 24 months.

The project addresses the development of the DPP-Framework, to support the TCs with the development of sector specific electrical and electronic product information forms, connecting to the DPP. The support also includes the analysis and harmonisation of existing standards for the electrical and electronic sector, and the coordination of the international IEC TC in the standardization work of the DPP System aspects and the TCs working on the DPP product data.

Relevant CLC TCs and their national mirror committees, involve but are not restricted to:

- Safety of household and similar electrical appliances
- Power electronics
- Performance of household and similar electrical appliances
- Industrial-process measurement, control and automation
- Product properties and classes and their identification
- Many more.

ID: 106**Title:** BatteryPass-Ready: Enabling Digital Product Passports for Batteries in the EU Regulatory Landscape**Time: 16:20****Project Reference:** BatteryPass-Ready; German Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action*Johannes Simböck**Acatech simboeck@acatech.de*

Abstract: With the entry into force of the EU Battery Regulation No. 2023/1542, Digital Product Passports (DPP) will be mandatory for all electric vehicle and light transport vehicle batteries as well as for industrial batteries > 2 kWh by February 2027. A decentralised system made up of interlinked components will be operated by the European Commission (registration), the distributor (decentralised data storage and provision) and IT service providers (backup). In view of the complexity of the overall project and its degree of novelty, the BatteryPass-Ready consortium develops a test environment allowing distributors and service providers to check their individual solutions for conformity with standards during the development phase. This environment should cover the following core functionalities, which would otherwise have to be created by each individual provider:

Keywords: Batteries, EU Regulation, Test Environment, DPP

- Definition of test procedures
- Analysing ongoing developments for mandatory data points and generating test data or incorporating test data provided by the user
- Execution, monitoring, and logging of tests
- Creation of emulation environments, in particular for components by the European Commission (e.g. registry)
- Connection of the systems to be tested and the data sources.

The test environment is used from a technical perspective (e.g. for interaction tests), for initial development and for maintenance and expansion. Furthermore, testing is carried out for the conformity of the DPP for new or updated products. In addition, the solution is to be used, for example, for connecting partners in the value-added system (e.g. for repair workshops). The work is carried out in close coordination with supporting stakeholders such as associations, e.g. VDA, VDMA, ZIV, and BITKOM. At the conference we would like to showcase the project set-up, its goals and involvement options. We further discuss challenges and the approach for a test environment in the current legislative landscape.

ID: 107**Time: 16:35****Title:** CIRPASS-2: Towards cross-pilot interoperability**Project Reference:** CIRPASS-2*Emrah Danisman**Beko emrah.danisman@beko.com***Abstract:**

Built on the results of the CIRPASS project, the CIRPASS-2 project is supporting 13 pilot deployments of DPP-enabled circular B2B use cases, across multiple complex value chains in the textiles, electronics, tires and construction sectors. The project aims to demonstrate DPP interoperability between the different pilots and confirm viable cross-sectoral, large-scale deployment of the DPP in real-life settings for identifiable and measurable environmental and economic benefits.

Towards this goal, the project works towards the development of a proposal for a reference architecture for the European DPP system and a proposal for a core ontology. The objective is that these proposals both align with the requirements of European legislation and standards but also with the beyond-regulatory needs of industry. The project also aims to closely follow and align to international frameworks and standards for DPPs, such as the United Nations Transparency Protocol.

This talk will present the CIRPASS-2 project's strategy for wide-scale piloting thanks to its 13 pilot ecosystems. It will then present in more detail one of the project's pilots led by BEKO.

Keywords: Textiles, Electronics, Tyres, Construction, EU Regulation, Wide-scale deployments of DPP, B2B circular use cases

Session 2 - Part 1: DPPs Barriers, Challenges and Opportunities.

Chairs: Salim Belouettar, Natalia Konchakova

This session explores how DPPs contribute to circular economy goals such as reuse, recycling, and waste reduction. Discussions will address implementation challenges, including data availability, privacy concerns, infrastructure, and costs. Case studies will showcase successful DPP applications across industries, demonstrating their potential to foster sustainability, compliance, and consumer trust.

ID: 201**Time: 17:10****Title:** Project “Fluid 4.0”: Digitalization and Circular Economy Enablement for the Fluid Power Industry**Project Reference:** Fluid 4.0, Funding code: 13IK039A, VDI Technologiezentrum GmbH*Martin Hankel**Bosch Rexroth AG martin.hankel@boschrexroth.de***Abstract:** Implementation of digitalization for fluid power industry. (Market volume of hydraulics and pneumatics product business about 70bil Euro)

Manufacturer, machine and system-builder and machine-user work together to develop standards in data structures and data models for digitalization and sustainability in 4 industry relevant new Use Cases. We are exploring digital data spaces for our industry and the benefits of data sharing also with competitors.

We want to use them for business and efficiency together with the upcoming Digital Product Passport.

Keywords: Fluid Power, Digital Twins, Energy Efficiency, CO₂ Balancing, Circular Economy, Digital Product Passport (DPP)**Use Case 1: System Development with Digital Twins**

- Applied to stationary (hydraulic presses) and mobile machines (excavators)
- System Digital Twin as an organizational unit for heterogeneous data sources
- Interaction concept between Digital Twins
- Connection to system simulation for model-based design and change management

Use Case 2: Energy Monitoring and Optimization of fluid power systems

- Application on hydraulic presses and Pneumatic handling systems
- Calculation and simulation of the current energy demand
- Implementation of energy-saving measures based on current electricity prices

Use Case 3: Cross-industry CO₂ balancing in use phase

- We know the carbon footprint from manufacturing its assets, but 98% of emissions are generated during use phase of the product
- Target: Standard to show CO₂ for the operation of fluid power products in systems and machines

Use Case 4: Circular Economy

- Create CE concept for the fluid power industry with potentials for business models about CE.
- Develop data structures for CE in Digital Twin to support CE business in fluid power industry

The project tests all concepts on real machines and production lines provided by industrial partners. Additional demonstrators serve as (open) testbeds for result dissemination. Engagement with CETOP, the European association for fluid power companies, ensures widespread discussion and adoption of the project's progress.

ID: 202

Time: 17:25

Title: Digital Product Passport for Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries and Carbon Felt Electrodes: Addressing Technical Challenges and Regulatory Compliance

Project Reference: GA no. 101137725 (BatCAT) and 101138510 (DigiPass CSA), Funded by Horizon Europe

Maria Bashir

Norwegian University of Life Sciences maria.bashir@nmbu.no

Abstract: The European Union's transition towards a circular economy has highlighted the Digital Product Passports (DPPs) as a critical measure to enhance transparency, traceability, sustainability, and compliance across product lifecycles. In the energy storage sector, vanadium redox flow batteries (VRFBs) and their carbon felt electrodes are of strategic relevance due to their high modularity, recyclability, and extended life. In this context, DPPs can play an important role in documenting material provenance, performance metrics, and end-of-life management introduced under the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and further align with EU Battery Regulation [3].

This study advances the EU's digital and green transition by developing a robust, scalable, and compliant DPP system in view of the technical requirements of VRFBs and carbon felt electrodes, addressing essential regulatory demands and practical challenges identified as critical factors in lifecycle management and circularity objectives. The DPP framework is designed to meet Annex XIII attributes requirement. Recent LCA research on VRFBs highlights the difficulty of capturing electrolyte cycles and carbon felt degradation data [4]. By addressing these data challenges, our implementation showcases more actionable circularity insights for vanadium-based storage systems.

To implement effective DPPs for VRFBs and carbon felt electrodes to ensure data-driven traceability and sustainability compliance across the battery value chain, our research explored a prototype architecture by utilizing Flutter, an open-source framework for cross-platform mobile/web development from a single codebase [1], and Firebase, a managed backend-as-a-service platform providing real-time database and user authentication support [2]. However, due to Firebase's U.S.-based data infrastructure, there are challenges for adaptability to varied deployment environments. Although this setup facilitated rapid development, it raised concerns about data residency and GDPR compliance with default data processing outside the European Union and poses potential compliance issues for European stakeholders, who might require on-premises solutions to meet data protection regulations.

To address this, a comparative analysis between the existing Firebase-based architecture and a proposed migration to a backend system architecture based on Django (a Python web framework) and PostgreSQL (a relational database) is underway, focusing on aspects such as control over data residency, scalability, and better regulatory compliance. This architecture enables secure, on-premises deployment or integration with EU-compliant cloud services. It aligns with GDPR principles and supports the structured management of access rights for different stakeholders, a requirement highlighted in the Battery Passport Technical Guidance [3].

References: [1] Google. Flutter Documentation. <https://flutter.dev> [2] Google. Firebase Documentation. <https://firebase.google.com> [3] Battery Pass Consortium. Battery Passport Technical Guidance, Version 1.0. 2024. <https://thebatteryass.eu> [4] Dieterle, M., Fischer, P., Pons, M.-N., Blume, N., Minke, C., Bischi, A. Life cycle assessment (LCA) for flow batteries: A review of methodological decisions. *Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments*, 53 (2022), 102457. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2022.102457>

Keywords: Vanadium Redox Flow Batteries, Circular Economy, Energy Storage, GDPR Compliance, Digital Product Passport (DPP)

ID: 203**Time: 17:40****Title:** Digital Battery Passport for Maritime Applications to Support Circular Economy**Project Reference:** eWAVE - Efficient HV-electric modular battery and distribution systems for sustainable WATERborne VEssels. Grant Agreement ID: 101192702; CINEA*Werner Rom**SYRION - Systemic Research and Innovation werner.rom@syrion.at***Abstract:**

The maritime sector faces significant challenges in the transition to fully electric, sustainable vessels. Key barriers include the low energy density of current battery systems, safety concerns, and the need for durable, sustainable materials. Economic viability also remains a major hurdle to widespread adoption. The planned EU Digital Battery Passport (DBP) is crucial to improve the uptake of batteries across the maritime sector, both on board and offshore, for 1st and 2nd life use. However, unlike the automotive industry, there has been relatively little focus on developing a DBP for maritime applications.

To address this gap, the EU project “eWAVE - Efficient high-voltage-electric modular battery and distribution systems for sustainable waterborne vessels” aims to develop a DBP specifically for maritime batteries. This passport is intended to serve as a core element for sustainable business models and to strengthen the circular economy. First, it will facilitate a “second life” for marine batteries — enabling their reuse in mobile or stationary applications, mainly on land — and support economically viable business models. Second, it will provide essential information on materials and design (e.g., recyclability, bio-based components, flame-retardant materials, system disassembly, etc.) in line with Design for Circularity as well as Safety and Sustainability by Design principles.

Building on pioneering initiatives such as the German Battery Pass project — mainly geared toward the automotive sector — eWAVE will focus on the specific conditions and requirements of shipping. A key feature of the project is the use of blockchain technology to ensure traceability, transparency, and real-time access to a battery’s historical data, enabling secure tracking throughout its lifecycle for both 1st and 2nd life applications. Ultimately, the project will develop tailored recommendations for the implementation of a DBP in electrified maritime applications.

Keywords: Digital Battery Passport (DBP), Circular Economy, Maritime Sector, Sustainable Vessels, Second Life, Battery Reuse, Battery Recycling, Battery Design for Circularity, Blockchain Technology, Battery Lifecycle, Sustainability by Design, High-voltage Electric Systems.

ID: 204**Title:** Circular & Sustainable Textiles & Clothing (CISUTAC) – A Step Toward a Circular Economy in Textiles**Time: 17:55****Project Reference:** CISUTAC: Circular & Sustainable Textiles & Clothing. Grant Agreement ID: 101060375; REA*Guy Buyle**Centexbel gbr@centexbel.be*

Abstract: The project CISUTAC (Circular and Sustainable Textiles and Clothing) aims at increasing circularity and sustainability in textiles and clothing in Europe. The production and consumption of textile products continue to grow, together with their impact on the environment, due to a lack of reuse, repair and recycling of materials. The objective of CISUTAC is to minimise the sector's total environmental impact by developing sustainable, novel, and inclusive large-scale European value chains.

Keywords: Sustainable Textiles, Textile Recycling, Textile Value Chain, Data Standardization, Reuse and Repair, Interoperability, Textile Industry Innovation, DPP in Textiles, EU Regulations on Textiles

CISUTAC contributes to the DPP development by bringing important input/standardized data to software platforms for customized product information retrieval. It targets a wide range of stakeholders, focusing on the professional actors along the value chain. The project wants to help to cover industry needs and gaps for data and the harmonisation of vocabulary and formats.

A guide on open data and its many facets is being compiled. This guide will include best practice recommendations and will focus on garments in general. It will include the experiences gained in the project. Therefore, the CISUTAC open data guide will provide formats that support consistent data input, use and exchange between stakeholders, ensuring for example access to data that enables sorting, reuse, repair and recycling.

The CISUTAC work on the DPP is implemented as much as possible in an aligned way with relevant other initiatives, e.g. the IRISS project, thanks to the involvement of several CISUTAC partners in such initiatives.

Poster session

ID: P1

Title: Provisions for the Inclusion of Safety Data in the Digital Materials Passports

Project Reference: MACRAME

Thomas Exner

Seven Past Nine GmbH thomas.exner@sevenpastnine.com

Abstract:

From the discovery and identification of a material to its end-of-life and possible circular re-integration, the value-chains and life-cycles of industrial materials are increasingly relying on digital approaches. The inclusion of safety data into the digital tracking of materials properties is not only a useful and sensible extra at this stage; rather, it is of utmost importance that the complex relationships between the structure, functionality and safety of a material are included into the data and design models that are being developed now to form the basis of the 'by design' character of fully digitalised materials value chains.

The MACRAMÉ Project has therefore devised an R&I approach, that widens the development of harmonised test guidelines (TGs) and guidance documents (GDs) (OECD) and standards (CEN, ISO) to market-relevant Advanced Materials (AdMas) s in their complex product matrices.

This will be achieved by defining the R&I Strategy through life-cycle assessment for five market-relevant industrial MACRAMÉ Use-Cases for the development of improved reporting guidelines combining community standards for materials characterisation and safety data with detailed descriptions of the complex product, biological and environmental matrices. In this course, the MACRAMÉ Information Hub has become the one-stop sharing platform for all Project partners; it ultimately aims to become directly integrated into advanced analysis, grouping and read-across applications, with the aim to strengthen European competitiveness.

MACRAMÉ's results ultimately aim to be processed and integrated into computational models for automatic data-gap filling and simulations, allowing the extension of models and approaches towards semi-automated digital workflows and guidance for future developments of decision support systems based on AI and machine learning.

Keywords: Sustainable by Design (SSbD), Sustainable Product Development, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Circular Economy, Sustainable Innovation

Title: Safety Testing of Emerging Products: The iCare Project and Its Contribution to Product Lifecycle Information

Project Reference: iCare (Grant agreement ID: 10109297) funded by EU HORIZON-CL4-2022-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-35 call

Elise Morel

TEMAS Solutions elise@temasol.ch

Abstract: Ensuring the safety of emerging and innovative products is an essential step for a transition towards a sustainable future. Important challenges are, however, faced when considering testing different life stages of a product. In the Horizon Europe project iCare (icareproject.eu), performance standards were used and adapted to generate representative samples for the use and end-of-life stages of various prototype products (i.e., car tyres, concrete, battery casings, printed inks, and storage tanks). Concentration and size selection protocols were deployed on the collected samples to meet (eco)toxicity assay requirements (e.g., size below 10 μm , 1 mg/L, and dispersible).

Keywords: (Eco)toxicity Testing, Product Lifecycle Assessment, Emerging Materials, Regulatory Compliance, Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)

The relevance and applicability of such (eco)toxicity results will be discussed in the context of regulatory compliance (e.g., general product regulation, construction product regulation) and safe and sustainable frameworks, with developments regarding the implications of such data for product lifecycle information and environmental impact assessments. This project has received funding from the EU Horizon Europe programme under Grant number 101092971, and its outcomes are critical for advancing the understanding of how product data can be used to evaluate the sustainability and safety of innovative products across their entire lifecycle.

Title: PSS-Pass: Digital Product Service System Passport for Circularity in Manufacturing

Project Reference: 101177594; HADEA

Kevin Nagorny

ATB Institut für angewandte Systemtechnik Bremen GmbH nagorny@atb-bremen.de

Abstract: Modern industrial companies aim to extend their products with services as fundamental value-added activities. The key potential of the concept of Product Service System (PSS), besides radical improvements in the use of products, is a reduction of environmental footprint of products and services. The overall footprint of PSS is still insufficiently investigated. The services within PSS are an important, insufficiently used source of (digitalized) data on the product and its use. It is likely that digital means facilitating provision of consistent “track and trace” information on the origin, composition and entire life cycle not only of a product but of all services offered and used around the product, will offer important contribution towards achievement of full circularity for manufacturing.

The key idea of PSS-Pass is to investigate how extension of DPP to Digital Product Service System Passport (DPSSP) can be effectively achieved and how it will allow for improved circularity of the manufacturing industry. The overarching hypothesis is that LCA underpinned by Machine Learning (ML) methods and informed by dynamic data paves the way to more accurate LCA while supporting PSS life cycle decision making. The collected and sharable data from DPSSP will allow to effectively apply ML as well as Digital Twin (DT) for more reliable decision-making processes concerning circularity of PSS.

The project will provide Methodological Framework for definition, development and update of DPSSP, Digital Environment for DPSSP built on existing interoperability architectures, a set of ontologies and context sensitive methods and tools used in a semantic layer for improved interoperability at DPSSP Environment, novel DT-based Simulation Framework, for PSS lifecycle analysis, and AI based method/tool to forecasts the environmental impact of PSS. The PSS-Pass solutions will be tested and evaluated within 3 pilots in diverse sectors: home appliances, complex equipment, and textile industry. ¹ATB Institut für angewandte Systemtechnik Bremen GmbH

Keywords: Digital Product Service System Passport (DPSSP), Circularity, Manufacturing, Machine Learning (ML), Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Digital Twin (DT), Sustainability, Interoperability, Data Sharing, Methodological Frameworks, Ontologies, Context-Sensitive Tools

Title: champ14.0ns - Enabling Intelligent and Sovereign Use of Data in Production

Project Reference: champ14.0ns, Program: Joint flagship project of the Austrian (FFG) and German (DLR-PT) Agencies, Grant Agreement ID: FO999925603

Arko Steinwender

Fraunhofer Austria Research GmbH arko.steinwender@fraunhofer.at

Abstract: The overarching goal of champ14.0ns is the further development of methods and tools that enable the intelligent and sovereign use of data in production. The project also explores the potential of cross-company data sharing in manufacturing, supported by real-world demonstrators. Two of four use cases focus on the DPP in the furniture industry and in wood material tracking

Leveraging connectors based on the Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC) framework, the project investigates how data space technologies can be applied for decentralized data management in the context of DPP systems. It addresses challenges for companies, and legal, technological, and organizational aspects of verifiable information exchange.

From a DPP data perspective, champ14.0ns analyzes the roles of data providers and consumers within the wood data ecosystem. Key focus areas include wood labeling, material tracking, and carbon footprint calculation. The project also tackles data modeling using knowledge graphs and ontologies, including the Circular Economy Ontology Network and Ontology Design Patterns.

After extensive discussions and workshops with industry partners, and as the project nears completion, it has become clear that interoperability remains one of the most significant challenges in enabling effective cross-company data exchange.

Keywords: Data Sovereignty, Cross-Company Data Sharing, Manufacturing, Verifiable Information Exchange, Carbon Footprint Calculation, Data Modeling, Knowledge Graphs, Ontologies, Circular Economy Ontology Network (CEON), Ontology Design Patterns, Interoperability, Transparency

Title: PASSAT - Supporting the Implementation of Digital Product Passports (DPPs)

Project Reference: PASSAT, FFG and DLR-PT, Grant Agreement ID: FO999925603

Arko Steinwender

Fraunhofer Austria Research GmbH arko.steinwender@fraunhofer.at

Abstract: PASSAT supports companies in the implementation of DPPs. The project develops practical solutions, regulatory recommendations, and training materials, and conducts pilot implementations in the textile, electronics, and ski industries. By doing so, PASSAT lays the groundwork for the broad adoption of DPPs in Austria and beyond.

The project takes a technology-neutral approach, systematically comparing and evaluating different technologies across relevant domains. This includes for example:

- Technologies and concepts for data interoperability, such as the UNTP, Eclipse Dataspace Connector, Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT), asset administration shell and HTTP-based approaches,
- Data carrier technologies, including QR codes, barcodes, RFID, and the innovative "seam coding" technique from Silana, where identifiers are sewed directly into the textile.

From a methodological perspective, PASSAT follows a structured, multi-phase approach:

- A broad screening of legal and technological requirements will be conducted, moving from a long list to a short list of viable options,
- The project will implement minimal DPPs containing approximately 10–15 core data points, enabling comparative analysis across use cases and technologies,
- These minimal DPPs will be further extended and enhanced in demonstration activities, exploring aspects such as verifiability, security, and data sovereignty.

In addition to the technical implementation, PASSAT addresses the economic dimensions of DPPs by conducting cost-benefit analyses, developing business model innovations, and assessing the macroeconomic impacts of DPP introduction.

Keywords:

Technology-Neutral Approach, Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT), Asset Administration Shell, QR Codes, Barcodes, RFID

Title: Centre of Excellence for Digital Product Passports - NL

Project Reference: CoE-DPP, Ministry of Economic Affairs, Department of Digital Economy, The Hague, The Netherlands

Sjoerd Rongen

TNO sjoerd.rongen@tno.nl

Abstract: Digital Product Passports are being introduced in a variety of sectors, through a multitude of policy developments, such as the battery regulation, toy regulation and ESPR. As well as a number of related initiatives such as the EU Customs reform. In the Netherlands, the responsibility of translating these European developments to national implementation is fragmented across various government institutions. Leading to inefficiencies in government and risking reduced interoperability between the various initiatives.

Keywords: Digital Product Passport, Ecosystem Development, Public-Private partnership, Cross-Sectoral collaboration, Scale up

At the same time, companies and organizations that aim to adopt DPPs are looking for solutions that ensures compliance with the various legislations as well as provides business benefit. Given the speed of development, and novelty of this topic, companies are often unable to implement a DPP solution on their own and are looking for support and guidance. However, they find a variety of projects, agencies, ecosystems and solutions all claiming to be the solution, often without these acknowledging the various other initiatives. This slows down DPP adoption by companies, and risks the creation of sectoral silos.

To solve for both of these challenges, TNO has created the Centre of Excellence for Digital Product Passports (CoE-DPP) in the Netherlands. In close collaboration with various government agencies, and launched by the ministry of Economic Affairs. This CoE-DPP was announced in February 2025 and is currently working on connecting the various Dutch DPP initiatives as well as providing an overview to both policy makers, and DPP implementing companies on what the current DPP ecosystem looks like and how value chain agreements surrounding the DPP may take shape. This serves to facilitate closer collaboration and faster DPP adoption, while ensuring higher value creation and interoperability between sectors.

Title: Preparing SMEs for Digital Product Passports: A Regional Knowledge Hub in Halland

Project Reference: Regional Feasibility Study

Maria Hammar

Chalmers Industriteknik maria.hammar@chalmersindustriteknik.se

Abstract:

With the upcoming EU Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), Digital Product Passports (DPPs) will become mandatory for a wide range of product categories. This feasibility study explores how small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the region of Halland, Sweden, can prepare for this shift and leverage early adoption of DPPs to enhance competitiveness and sustainability. SMEs represent 95% of all companies in Europe and in the region of Halland it is even as much as 99%.

The project investigates the prerequisites for establishing a regional knowledge hub that can support SMEs with information, guidance, and training related to DPP implementation. Activities include surveys, workshops, and stakeholder dialogues to identify needs, opportunities, and gaps in knowledge and capacity.

By facilitating collaboration among regional actors and promoting digital and circular business models, the initiative aims to pave the way for a permanent support structure that helps SMEs comply with upcoming legislation and thrive in a data-driven product landscape. The project is managed by Chalmers Industriteknik in collaboration with EMC and funded by Tillväxtverket and Region Halland.

Keywords: Digital Product Passports (DPP), SMEs, Ecodesign Regulation (ESPR), Circular Economy, Knowledge Hub, Sustainable Innovation, Halland

Title: Enhancing DPP implementation through a digital Quality Infrastructure: Data Spaces and beyond

Project Reference: QI-Digital Projekt funded by the German Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy

Anna Maria Elert

Bundesanstalt für Materialforschung und -prüfung (BAM) anna-maria.elert@bam.de

Abstract: An integrated, digital ecosystem for the Quality Infrastructure (QI) will contribute to leverage the implementation of the Digital Product Passport (DPP) at system and organizational level. The information required for the DPP are fundamentally rooted in the QI which comprises all processes, tools and policies to ensure the quality, safety and sustainability of products.

As of today, these processes and documentation are largely paper-based and require burdensome bureaucratic efforts, with shortcomings regarding traceability and verification on information delivered along the value chains and towards authorities.

The mission of our initiative QI-Digital is to digitalize the entire QI process chain, transforming every element—metrology, standardization, accreditation, conformity assessment and market surveillance—into a fully digital, interoperable, and future-ready digital QI ecosystem. To this end, QI-Digital is building a **Digital QI Toolbox** that includes machine-readable data formats for certificates and other conformity documents, standardized interfaces, and verifiable digital credentials for QI actors.

The **DPP** will deliver structured, machine-readable, and trustworthy information across a product's entire life cycle—covering quality, sustainability, and all legally required conformity evidence. The Digital Certificate of Conformity and fully digital test reports as part of the QI-Digital toolbox provide this information in native digital form, enabling end-to-end automation of evidence creation, exchange, and verification for the DPP.

The heart of the digital ecosystem for QI is Quality-X. This concept is designed to facilitate the sovereign exchange of QI data within federated data spaces. QI actors, such as testing laboratories, manufacturers, and regulators, are identified, and authorized through the use of verified credentials, ensuring the integrity and security of the data shared. With digitally mapped value creation flows in data spaces, test flows are also to be established in the same way, which, in reverse, enables the machine-readable verification of process data against digital norms and standards in real time without media discontinuity. By retrieving verified data directly from authoritative sources, the DPP evolves from a static information repository into a dynamic trust platform, supporting regulatory compliance while unlocking new opportunities for business innovation.

QI-Digital is a joint initiative of five key organizations in Germany's Quality Infrastructure (QI): the Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing (BAM), the German Accreditation Body (DAkkS), the German Institute for Standardization (DIN), the German Commission for Electrical, Electronic & Information Technologies of DIN and VDE (DKE) and the National Metrology Institute of Germany (PTB).

Keywords: Digital QI Toolbox, Machine-readable certificates, Quality X, Quality Infrastructure, Digital Quality Documents, DPP, Data Spaces, QI Ecosystem

Title: The DPP as a facilitator of high granularity information to industries, territories and regions

Project Reference: THESEUS

Kostas Chatziioannou

Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) kostas.chatziioannou@iccs.gr

Abstract:

Theseus H4C project will develop adjustable schemes for dynamically updated Digital Product Passport (DPP) modified and specialized accordingly per circular product and related material flow. The development will include the following steps:

1. DPP design at data and architecture level. Define static and dynamic information to be included based on existing regulations, state of the art analysis and consultations with stakeholders.
2. technical development of an alpha version with live update mechanism and user-friendly interface.
3. demonstrate DPP and perform necessary modifications per case.
4. testing and collecting feedback from the users.
5. Final version of the DPP. DPP will be combined with a set of digital tools to enhance their modules, develop and fully exploit other sophisticated features.

The set will be integrated in the central Theseus platform and includes tools facilitating:

- Material Flow Analysis (MFA): DPP will expand the granularity of the MFA and expand its scope.
- Improved logistics: DPP combined with logistics aspects, will integrate the territorial dimension in the decision making.
- Matchmaking and synergies identification: DPP will be used to feed critical input for the identification of synergies or/and for further informed decision making on the opportunities identified by these features.
- LCA, predictions, optimization, Scheduling and financial tools: DPP will feed critical data as input to these tools improving their efficiency.

Additionally, an MR application will be developed to facilitate value chain interactions as the events in product lifecycle take place through immersive visualizations, assisting end user to obtain information about available resources and enabling informed decisions for resource efficiency (e.g., for repurposing, recycling, reduce, etc.). MR tool will be fed via Theseus central platform with information on user interactions, ML object detection and positional awareness. The Dynamic DPP developed in Theseus H4C to serve regional context, will offer added value in the following user groups:

- Industries: by optimizing, identifying opportunities and simulating potential scenarios of changes and process innovations internally, as well as by identifying synergies and opportunities within their territory and region with other industries, or by attracting innovation actors to develop novel solutions and features on the value chains.
- Regulators, Regional Authorities: by exploiting powerful decision and policy making tools, developing strategies and action plans on materials, transportation, utilities and infrastructures, creating and improving standards and metrics.

Keywords: DPP, Hub4Circularity, Industrial Symbiosis, Industry, Regional

Session 2 - Part 2: DPPs Barriers, Challenges and Opportunities.

Chairs: Salim Belouettar, Natalia Konchakova

ID: 205

Title: CE-RISE: Enabling Circularity Through Digital Product Passports and Open Data Systems

Time: 09:20

Project Reference: 101092281; Horizon Europe (EC)

Miguel Las Heras Hernández

NILU mher@nilu.no

Abstract: The Circular Economy seeks to eliminate material loss by reintroducing products into the value chain post-use. Achieving this requires reliable, accessible information. To support sustainable production and resource efficiency, the EU mandates Digital Product Passports (DPPs) to ensure trustworthy product data. However, the surge in data requires standardized processing and interpretation to drive real impact.

Keywords: Digital Product Passport (DPP), Open Data Systems, Circular Economy, Data Model, Data Harmonization, Resource Efficiency, Interoperability, Product Environmental Footprint (PEF), Repair, Reuse, Remanufacturing,

Launched in 2023, the Horizon Europe CE-RISE project aims to establish an open-access information system by 2026. This proof-of-concept will demonstrate how smarter information management can enable sustainable, circular practices across the electronics value chain. Data will be aggregated from various DPP service providers, ERP systems, and organizational inputs. CE-RISE will support structured data reading/writing across platforms, ensuring interoperability and system cohesion.

By merging, harmonizing, and processing product data, CE-RISE will supply key functionalities for circular strategies. These include open access to information on critical raw materials, hazardous substances, R-strategy potential (repair, reuse, remanufacture, etc.), handling guides, disassembly manuals, and more. The system will also provide open access to Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) calculations, ensuring circularity aligns with broader sustainability goals. Secure data sharing among value chain actors will be supported, maintaining confidentiality while enhancing collaboration.

This presentation explores CE-RISE's data model development to tackle interoperability challenges. We'll show how the model enables seamless integration of diverse data sources—ERP systems, DPP providers, manual inputs—and enhances DPP usability. Finally, we'll highlight its role in shaping DPP structures for electronics and its potential to serve as a blueprint across other sectors.

ID: 206

Title: NEO-CYCLE - Sustainable Upcycling of Spent NdFeB Magnets and the Integration of Digital Product Passports (DPPs)

Time: 09:35

Project Reference: EU, Grant Agreement ID: 101138058*Arko Steinwender**Fraunhofer Austria Research GmbH arko.steinwender@fraunhofer.at***Keywords:**

Abstract: The NEO-CYCLE project aims to demonstrate, at TRL 6, the sustainable upcycling of spent NdFeB magnets sourced from hard disk drives (HDDs). The project targets the production of high-quality end products for four specific case studies: the pharmaceutical, ammonia, fertilizer, and polymer industries. It also addresses the necessary steps for achieving market uptake.

From a DPP data perspective, the project explores:

- Potential DPP content for electronic devices at end-of-life,
- The economic viability of tracking DPP data across different processes,
- The concept of material passports for critical raw materials, and
- The integration of product and material passports into the new DPPs of upcycled products.

The general transformation of product and material passports is also addressed. The development of the NEO-CYCLE DPP data ecosystem actively involves all key stakeholders along the value chain from public authorities to WEEE recycling companies, technology developers, industry associations, NGOs, SMEs, and commercial companies in the targeted sectors. Special attention is given to the calculation of social sustainability KPIs.

From a DPP system-perspective, the focus lies on the UNTP. The project builds on the DPP-related open-source results (implemented with distributed ledger and blockchain) developed by the University of Catalonia and others, such as: <https://ereuse.org/en/tag/dpp/> and <https://idhub.pangea.org/help/en/community/>

ID: 207**Title:** Governance Framework for Digital Product Passports in the Furniture Sector – The R-Evolve Project**Time: 09:50****Project Reference:** Horizon Europe Project R-Evolve, DG RTD, Project Number 101182221*Holger Berg**Wuppertal Institut holger.berg@wupperinst.org*

Abstract: The contribution will present the approach to and the results of creating a governance framework for Digital Product passports (DPP) for the furniture sector under development in the project R-Evolve. The Framework shall stimulate Circular Economy (CE) and incentivise data sharing while aiming to cater for the protection requirements of the stakeholder groups involved. Such governance frameworks are only just being developed for most DPP-oriented projects and approaches. These frameworks aim to complement DPP-technology and system architecture development by determining the rules, rights and obligations of the stakeholders participating in DPP systems. They also complement regulations and standards by explicating more distinctively rules for the use and employment of DPP systems as well as the (CE-oriented) cooperation and data exchange therein.

Keywords: Data Sharing, Stakeholder Cooperation, Legislation, ESPR, Standardisation, CEN/CENELEC JTC 24, Co-Creation, Business Models, Circular Product Design, Collaborative Innovation

The governance framework is created on the premises of the current legislative and standardisation processes (ESPR and JTC 24 respectively), furniture-specific approaches to Circular Economy, co-creation sessions with stakeholders, and the creation of dedicated use cases and user stories. For the latter we build on the involvement of R&D pilots in R-Evolve that address the realisation of several Circular Economy strategies through data provision.

R-evolve focuses on developing solutions for furniture design and business models that prioritise sustainability. It aims to systematically support the furniture industry's transition, emphasizing CE-oriented Product-System Innovations, including CE-oriented Business Models, circular material and product design strategies, and the use of the Digital Product Passport.

ID: 208

Title: DYMAN DPPs and DBLs for Cooling Technologies in Data Centres: Enabling Interoperable, Lifecycle-Based Digital Information Exchange

Time: 10:05

Project Reference: DYMAN GA: 101161930*Emre Yontem**Ekodenge AS Turkey emre.yontem@eco-wise.co.uk***Abstract:**

DYMAN (GA: 101161930) is an ongoing EIC-Pathfinder project aiming to develop a new adsorption chiller design using novel low-temperature absorbents and advanced adsorption heat exchangers, dynamically managed within data centres. As part of DYMAN, we are advancing our Ecowise integrated suite of Digital Product Passports (DPPs) and Digital Building Logbooks (DBLs) tailored for the cooling and HVAC sector and their host buildings.

Ecowise DPPs and DBLs will support the first deployment of a dynamic, lifecycle-based DPP for cooling technologies, compliant with emerging interoperability standards. These DPPs will include energy consumption data, durability indicators, and circularity metrics such as maintenance logs and usage data, enabling assessment of end-of-use value and informed refurbishment decisions. The DBLs, in parallel, will provide building-level traceability and KPI reporting for data centres aligned with (EU) 2024/1364.

This will also mark the first integration of linked DPPs and DBLs in the cooling domain—enabling technical data exchange (e.g. COP, capacity), lifecycle records (manufacturing to disposal), and energy data visualisation. Ecowise systems will interface with existing Building Management Systems (BMS) and the DYMAN management platform, ensuring interoperability and verifiability from a single-entry point. These innovations will be validated at TRL 4–5 through virtual piloting, with real-use data expected to support advancement toward TRL 5.

Keywords: Digital Building logbooks, data centers, linked DPPs

Session 3: Technical Requirements and Implementation of DPPs.

Chairs: Peter Klein, Natalia Konchakova

This session will explore digital platforms and tools that can support the successful implementation of DPPs. Discussions will cover data interoperability, governance structures, and integration of open digital infrastructures to support circularity. Specific topics include the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the EUDAT collaborative data infrastructure and role of national research data infrastructures, material data repositories, semantic interoperability, decentralized digital identities and persistent identifiers, data immutability and blockchain solutions. Additionally, the session addresses open research data and intellectual property rights (IPR) in data sharing. Contributions from Large Research Infrastructures (LRIs), Open Innovation Platforms and Test Beds (OIPs and OITBs), Materials Acceleration Platforms (MAPs), Factories of the Future (FoF), and Digital Innovation Hubs will be explored.

ID: 301

Title: Innovation by Design – supporting Digital Maturity of Advanced Materials Communities

Time: 11:00

Project Reference: DigiPass CSA

Natalia Konchakova

Helmholtz Zentrum Hereon natalia.konchakova@hereon.de

Abstract: DigiPass EU project has as one overarching objective to bolster the digital maturity of European stakeholders from different materials development communities, with a particular emphasis on small and medium enterprises (SMEs). In this talk, we will present an overview on an inventory of information sources and accreditation processes used by communities and stakeholders involved in advanced materials design and manufacturing for composites and pre-painted metals industries. We will also discuss the importance to increase the level of digital maturity of European universities and academia. In particular, the increase of the TRL level of scientific data will enable their utilization in Digital Product Passports (DPP) and thus drive innovation-by-design approaches.

Keywords:

Digitalization, Sustainability, Data & Knowledge sharing, Digital Materials & Product Passport, Digital Maturity enhancement

Another central objective of DigiPass CSA is to couple regulatory aspects with collaborative products innovation processes on federated dataspace, thus allowing for a seamless transition from research to production. The Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) is the central document which strives to improve for instance on products' circularity, carbon footprint, and other environmental sustainability aspects. Effective legislation and regulation supporting the digital transformation is currently under way, enforcing Digital Product Passports (DPP) for some industrial areas and products. The DPPs need to get implemented as part of industrial production in a collaborative fashion along distributed production- and value-chains. The integration and role of the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) principles for establishment of a DPP will be discussed. We will point the importance of the SSbD community input to collect requirements and limitations in the advanced materials data documentation and management correlated to the Digital Passport.

Moreover, an example to support a digital maturity of universities and SMEs by digitalization of materials' data and integration of AI/ML and physics-based modeling approaches to VIPCOAT Open Innovation Platform will be showcased. The contributions of both DigiPass and VIPCOAT projects would support industry and academia to follow the Competitiveness Compass of the European Commission.

Acknowledgement: **DigiPass CSA**, HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-39, GA No. 101138510, WIKKI LIMITED, UK participant in Horizon Europe Project DigiPass, is supported by UKRI grant number 10100819. <https://ms.hereon.de/digipass/index.php.en>

VIPCOAT, H2020-NMBP-TO-IND-2020, GA No. 952903. <https://vipcoat-oip.com/welcome>

ID: 302**Time: 11:15**

Title: Accelerating the Digital and Green Transitions through Semantic Interoperability: The Onto-DESIDE Project and Digital Product Passports

Project Reference: Onto-DESIDE - Grant Agreement No. 101058682; European Commission (Horizon Europe Programme)

Huanyu Li

Linköping University huanyu.li@liu.se

Abstract: The Onto-DESIDE (<https://ontodeside.eu/>) project is a Horizon Europe action, aiming to accelerate the digital and green transitions by targeting the information sharing and semantic interoperability challenges. The goal is to provide support for information flows in the Circular Economy, grounded in open web standards.

Keywords: Circular Economy, Semantic Web, Ontologies, Digital Product Passport, Open Circularity Platform

Key project results include a technology platform and methods for secure, decentralized data sharing of materials and product data globally, which can provide a basis for DPP data sharing. Three use cases, from different industry domains (i.e. textile, electronics, construction), have driven the research and development activities and served as test beds and demonstrators for cross-industry applicability.

The presentation will demonstrate key components of the project results, including (1) the Circular Economy Ontology Network (CEON), for CE data documentation, (2) the Open Circularity Platform, showcasing how the Solid (<https://solidproject.org>) family of emerging standards can facilitate CE data sharing, and (3) an enhanced Circularity Thinking methodology, expanding the current Climate KIC approach (<https://www.climate-kic.org/spotlight-initiatives/circularity-thinking-programme/>) with new tools for innovation and analysis of CE value networks. In addition, we will show example material and information flow mappings across the three industry domains studied, along with evaluations of the aforementioned solutions in these three cases.

Finally, we will exemplify how a Digital Product Passport Ontology (DPPO) (<https://w3id.org/dppo/>) can be modelled and used to address semantic interoperability and data sharing for DPP systems, using the same set of technologies, which is further validated based on examples from the textile and electronics use cases in Onto-DESIDE.

ID: 303**Title:** Modular Architecture for Digital Product Passports (DPPs) for Critical Raw Materials: Enhancing Sustainability, Compliance, and Circularity**Time: 11:30****Project Reference:** MaDiTraCe project, 101091502, European Commission (Horizon Europe)*Doruk Sahinel**Spherity doruk.sahinel@spherity.com*

Abstract: Digital Product Passports (DPPs) and verifiable identities build the digital backbone for the circular economy in Europe, enabling traceability, compliance, and data-driven collaboration for critical raw material supply chains. Key EU frameworks (Battery Regulation, ESPR, CS3D) require DPPs to include detailed supply chain information to improve product traceability.

Keywords: Critical Raw Materials, Circular Economy, Self-Sovereign Identity, Verifiable Credentials, Data Traceability, Modular Architecture

The MaDiTraCe project recognizes that DPPs can be more than regulatory tools. When integrated within an architecture based on trust and data sovereignty, they can enhance compliance, sustainability, and circularity. This contribution presents the modular architecture developed in MaDiTraCe to support DPPs for critical raw materials. It ensures that all data is accurate, traceable, and issued by a legitimate source, enabling compliance with verification processes.

The architecture relies on self-sovereign identity (SSI), verifiable credentials (VCs), and decentralized identifiers (DIDs). DPP data attributes are stored in standardized formats, aligned with cross-sectoral initiatives like Catena-X, CIRPASS, and the Battery Pass Consortium. To ensure interoperability, open standards such as W3C VCs enable direct connectivity among stakeholders using SSI principles. The did:ebis identifier, based on the European Blockchain Services Infrastructure, is used to ensure DPP data and verifications remain accessible over time.

A preliminary risk analysis identified the need for data security and integrity. In response, an optional blockchain layer enables on-demand notarization, reinforcing data trustworthiness without compromising modularity.

An ongoing research direction explores integrating material and artificial fingerprints into the DPP. While these offer strong potential to anchor physical products—and their geographical provenance—to digital counterparts, challenges remain in standardization, interoperability, and secure linkage to verifiable credentials.

ID: 304**Time: 11:45**

Title: Leveraging AI for Circular Value Chains: The ENCIRCLE Project and Blockchain-Enabled Digital Product Passports

Project Reference: ENCIRCLE - Grant Agreement No. 101178230; European Commission (Horizon Europe Programme)

Nikolaos Dimitriou

Centre for Research & Technology (CERTH) / Information Technologies Institute (ITI)

nikdim@iti.gr

Abstract: The ENCIRCLE project leverages AI-driven innovation to establish circular value chains. Central to its approach is the DPP, a blockchain-enabled repository that securely manages product traceability, lifecycle data, and sustainability metrics.

ENCIRCLE aims to deploy and scale DPP implementations in two manufacturing use cases: the steel and home appliances industries. A key technical contribution of ENCIRCLE is the development of a blockchain-enabled track-and-trace framework, which equips each product with a DPP prototype at market readiness. This passport builds upon ZINQ's existing prototype DCPD for the steel industry and integrates sustainability and circularity data—both directly measured and AI-estimated—and is stored on secure, tamper-proof blockchain infrastructure. Energy efficient consensus algorithms (e.g., Proof-of-Stake) are leveraged to maximize energy efficiency, while authentication and authorization protocols verify that only validated stakeholders (e.g., manufacturers, distributors, recyclers) can access appropriate product data.

Industrial IoT sensors coupled with AI-driven methodologies, such as soft sensors and Digital Twins, establish a Virtual Production Line, facilitating real-time monitoring and lifecycle auditing from production to end-of-life, enriching the DPP with actionable and updatable data. To support the circular economy, ENCIRCLE introduces an AI-supported DPP wallet mobile app based on decentralized applications. This consumer oriented wallet targeting the home appliances use case enables users to register, track, and manage their products.

A Digital Marketplace powered by AI recommendation systems delivers personalized offers to consumers for product recycling, resale, or refurbishment. AR enhanced by Computer Vision algorithms (semantic segmentation, object detection) provides real-time sustainability insights and interactive guidance for product repair and maintenance, accessible through smart glasses or mobile devices.

Keywords: Blockchain, Sustainability Metrics, Track-and-Trace Framework, Industrial IoT, Digital Twins, AI-Powered Marketplace, Augmented Reality (AR), Consumer Engagement, Blockchain Technology, Energy-Efficient Consensus Algorithms

ID: 305**Title:** Enabling Circular Economy with Digital Product Passports: The DaCapo Project**Time: 12:20****Project References:** HEU DaCapo (Grant Agreement No. 101091780) European Commission*Kristiina Valtanen**VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland kristiina.valtanen@vtt.fi*

Abstract: The DaCapo project aims to develop human-centric digital tools and services to promote the adoption of circular economy practices within manufacturing and product life cycles. It targets the manufacturing sector with three pilot products from aeronautics, consumer electronics, and warehousing. For each pilot, a Digital Product Passport (DPP) solution has been developed among other DaCapo tools. The DaCapo DPP is designed not only for regulatory compliance but also as a facilitator for circular economy practices, serving as an enabler and gateway for applications such as the Electronic Maintenance Book.

Keywords: Digital Product Passport, Ecodesign Regulation, Standardization, Interoperability, Carbon Footprint

The technical design of the DaCapo DPP is based on Asset Administration Shells (AAS), combined with the Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) framework to address data sovereignty requirements. Tooling frameworks such as Semantic Treehouse are being explored for semantic modeling of DPP data and for mapping DPP data to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) ontologies.

The development of the DaCapo DPP focuses on minimum-viable prototyping, relevance to project use cases, post-project extensibility, and adherence to legislation and industry best practices. The DPP integrates with various other DaCapo tools: the Modular Digital Thread tool functions as a product-centered data management scheme within the OEM, linking product, process, and resource data flows, while the GRETA sustainability calculation tool provides updated assessments of sustainable and circular economy indicators for DPP. The DaCapo platform also includes middleware featuring an Orion Context Broker establishing a data lake and interoperable layer for the DaCapo platform.

Validation of the DaCapo platform and DPP will occur through didactic factory facilities of DaCapo RTOs as well as real production environments. Further development of the DPP concept will proceed under another EU Horizon project, DigInTraCE, through the integration of smart tagging solutions into DPP.

ID: 306**Time: 12:35**

Title: Advancing Sustainable Industries through Data-Driven Digital Product Passport Solutions: TVS' Pioneering Role in European Innovation

Project References: JIDEP (GA - 101058732) HE, RESTORE (GA - 101138775) HE, ALABAMA (GA - 101138842) HE, GEAR-UP (GA - 101178484) HE

Farhad Arifin

Technovative Solutions Ltd. farhad@technovativesolutions.co.uk

Abstract: Technovative Solutions Ltd. (TVS) is at the forefront of pioneering secure, scalable, and interoperable Digital Product Passport (DPP) frameworks designed to accelerate Europe's transition to a circular and transparent economy. With a focus on the European Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), TVS leads innovations in DPP technologies across a range of industries, including batteries, automotive, plastics, aerospace, marine, textiles, and medical devices.

Through multiple EU-funded initiatives such as BASE, RESTORE, ALABAMA, ENCORE, ECOPLAST, GEAR-UP, and JIDEP, TVS leverages advanced data space technologies and Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) to facilitate sovereign, user-controlled data exchange. TVS' solutions align with international standards, including International Data Spaces (IDS), Gaia-X, and Catena-X, and support both bespoke and integrative ecosystem models that foster compliance, data-driven services, and collaboration across value chains.

Key features of TVS' DPP frameworks include the integration of Circularity Calculators and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) tools, enabling the evaluation of ecodesign, benchmarking of circularity, and creation of Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs). These capabilities help combat greenwashing and increase transparency across complex global supply chains.

Noteworthy achievements include leading the Digital Battery Passport in the BASE project, creating a DPP and marketplace for remanufacturing in RESTORE, and contributing to sustainable manufacturing initiatives in GEAR-UP and ALABAMA. In ECOPLAST, TVS is deploying a blockchain-enabled DPP for tracing recycled automotive plastics and facilitating third-party certification.

By developing interoperable digital ecosystems and providing customized sustainability tools, TVS is empowering industries to exceed compliance requirements and drive Europe's green transition, helping shape the future of product traceability.

Keywords: Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), Circularity Calculators, Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs), Greenwashing, International Data Spaces (IDS), Gaia-X, Catena-X, Product Traceability, European Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), Blockchain, Remanufacturing, Recycling, Automotive Plastics, Digital Battery Passport, Supply Chain Transparency

ID: 307**Title:** Battery Digital Product Passport Demonstrator in Horizon Europe BatWoMan**Time: 12:50****Project Reference:** 101069705 – BatWoMan, Horizon Europe*Margit Kranner**AIT Austrian Institute of Technology margit.kranner@ait.ac.at*

Abstract: As a key enabler for the circular economy, a product passport aims to ensure transparency, traceability, and sustainability across a product's lifecycle. In our project, we have developed a demonstrator for a battery-specific DPP, leveraging emerging technologies to facilitate secure and interoperable data exchange between stakeholders.

Our DPP concept provides a structured and verifiable record of essential product information throughout the battery's lifecycle. It enables manufacturers, regulators, and recycling companies to access and update relevant data securely.

The passport stores key attributes, including material composition, production details, usage history, and recycling instructions. It also supports compliance with regulatory frameworks such as the EU Battery Regulation. The demonstrator is built using a decentralized data-sharing architecture based on Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC) and Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) principles. Key technologies include:

- Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) & Verifiable Credentials (VCs): Ensuring authenticity and integrity of data.
- Interoperable Data Exchange via EDC: Facilitating secure and standardized data transactions between entities.
- Docker-based Deployment: Enabling modular and scalable implementation.
- QR Code Integration: Linking physical products to their digital passports for instant verification and access.
- Decentralized Anchoring: Enhancing data trustworthiness through external, federated Trust Frameworks (GAIA-X)

The demonstrator simulates a simplified battery lifecycle scenario where data is collected from manufacturers and made accessible for recycling companies to update the passport. The DPP allows stakeholders to retrieve necessary information through a web-based interface, ensuring efficient decision-making and compliance tracking.

By developing this DPP demonstrator, we demonstrate how digitalization can support sustainability and regulatory compliance in the battery sector. Our approach ensures that all lifecycle data is transparent, trustworthy, and accessible, contributing to a more circular and responsible battery ecosystem.

Keywords: Battery, Digital Product Passport (DPP), EU Battery Regulation, Circular Economy, Interoperability, Data Integrity, Decentralized Architecture, Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC), Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI), Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs), Verifiable Credentials (VCs), Trust Frameworks,

ID: 308

Title: RecAI Digital Product Passport: Enhancing Traceability and Transparency in the Aluminum Supply Chain

Time: 13:05

Project Reference: 101138747; EU Grant Agreement*Symeonidis Panagiotis**Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (CERTH) psymeonidis@iti.gr***Keywords:**

Abstract: The RecAI Digital Product Passport (DPP) is developed to improve traceability, transparency, and regulatory compliance within the aluminum supply chain. This work presents the DPP system's initial design and architecture centered on distributed ledger technology (DLT) and blockchain-based smart contracts. The implementation aligns with the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), a cornerstone of the EU's Circular Economy Action Plan, which mandates the deployment of DPPs for sustainable and recyclable goods.

By utilizing permissioned blockchain frameworks such as Hyperledger Fabric, the RecAI DPP enables secure, verifiable, and tamper-resistant data sharing among aluminum supply chain stakeholders. The platform supports material traceability, verification of recycled content, and automated compliance monitoring against ESPR sustainability benchmarks. Core features integrated into the system architecture include material composition tracking, carbon footprint monitoring, and lifecycle impact assessment, promoting data interoperability and streamlined regulatory reporting.

Decentralized data infrastructure is essential for enabling such DPP-technology, allowing companies to share product data securely while retaining full control, sovereignty and ownership. In the core of the DPP, lies a RecAL-Hub, the federated data ecosystem / data mesh running on shared technical components - enabling trusted, interoperable data exchange across RecAL partner organizations. Unlike centralized systems, decentralized architecture supports data sovereignty and better suited to the complex, cross-domain or even multiple-stakeholder data for DPP.

The study also addresses technical challenges associated with DPP implementation, particularly the need for standardized data schemas and scalable infrastructure. The outcomes contribute to the broader digital transformation of industrial supply chains, proposing a flexible and extensible framework for sustainable product governance.

Session 4: Emerging Technologies for DPPs.

Chairs: Carolynn Bernier, Kostas Chatziioannou

This session explores the role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and emerging technologies in the development and optimization of Digital Product Passports (DPPs). It will examine how AI can be leveraged for data analysis and management, improving the accuracy, efficiency, and scalability of DPP systems. AI-driven solutions, including predictive analytics and automation, will be discussed as key enablers for enhancing DPP functionality. Additionally, the session will highlight the potential of digital twins and other emerging technologies to support real-time monitoring, simulation, and decision-making processes, ultimately advancing the effectiveness of DPPs in promoting sustainability and circular economy objectives.

ID: 401

Title: TRICK- PRODUCT Data Traceability from cradle to cradle by blockchains interoperability and sustainability service marketplace

Time: 14:40

Project Reference: Grant agreement ID: 958352 - HADEA

Alessandro Canepa

Piacenza 1733 alessandro.canepa@piacenza1733.it

Abstract: An assessment by the EU Parliament of 232 active ecolabels in Europe concluded that almost half of the labels' verification was either weak or not carried out. This alarming figure underscores the urgency of deploying automated tools for verification of the future Digital Product Passport (DPP) declarations.

The anti-counterfeiting AI service developed in the TRICK project addresses a growing concern: the falsification of environmental (green) declarations related to textile products, especially as Europe mandates Digital Product Passports (DPPs) under the Ecodesign regulation. While traditional counterfeit detection has focused on finished products (e.g., luxury fakes), this new layer of deception targets sustainability claims that are harder to verify, such as recycled content or ethical sourcing. This fraud severely undermines honest companies investing in sustainability and gives an unfair competitive advantage to those making false claims.

The system was designed with direct input from the Italian Customs Agency, who identified the most frequently falsified elements in declarations: raw material composition, production milestones, and timing of processes. These declarations are typically part of Export Shipment Dossiers (ESD), which Customs uses during inspections. The new AI tool analyzes these data points to flag anomalies that suggest deception. The tool's goal is not just compliance, but fairness—ensuring that EU companies committed to circular and sustainable practices are not penalized by an uneven playing field created by deceit.

Keywords: Digital Product Passport (DPP), Traceability, Blockchain, Sustainability Verification, Anti-Counterfeiting, Artificial Intelligence (AI)

ID: 402

Time: 14:55

Title: Project title: AIDEAS - DPPs for manufacturing machines**Project Reference:** This research was funded by European Union's by Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programs AIDEAS under Grand Agreement No 101057294 and W2W under Grand Agreement No 101138789.*Georgia Kougka**CERTH - Center for Research and Technology Hellas kougka@iti.gr***Abstract:** The Digital Product Passport (DPP) is an innovative tool designed to revolutionize product transparency and sustainability within the global economy. Acting as a digital twin of physical products, the DPP consolidates comprehensive lifecycle data, including material sourcing, manufacturing processes, usage, and end-of-life recycling.

In this presentation we will dive into DPPs for manufacturing machines (AIDEAS1) and the Wood Sector (W2W2). In the first case, this of Manufacturing Machines (AIDEAS) the Machine Passport (MP) serves as a digital product passport that captures and organizes all critical lifecycle data of industrial equipment from design and manufacturing to use and end-of-life stages. More specifically, MP integrates the real-time input of sensors, maintenance records and performance data to enable predictive maintenance and traceability, while sustainability is supported. Whereas in the "Wood Sector (W2W)", we have developed a comprehensive application that allows users to explore a wide range of wood types, each accompanied by detailed and structured information. Users can effortlessly export or update data, and the integration of QR codes ensures direct navigation to specific entries within the application, enhancing usability in real-world settings like warehouses or workshops. To further improve the user experience, we've embedded AI-powered summarization models that generate concise overviews of the wood data—removing the need to scroll through endless tables.

Building on these applications, we now turn to the broader vision of how Digital Product Passports can transform industry practices and enrich user experiences. With the DPPs developed for AIDEAS and W2W as concrete examples, we explore how such tools can support the shift toward a circular economy. A key focus is the integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) to enable more automated, yet customized, generation of DPPs across different contexts. Looking ahead, we are embedding Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) systems powered by intelligent agents, allowing users to interact with the DPPs through natural language queries and receive insightful, contextualized responses based on real-time data from the underlying systems. This capability not only enhances usability but also empowers stakeholders to derive deeper value from the data captured throughout a product's lifecycle. Furthermore, we are expanding interoperability with enterprise systems—such as digital twins—and aligning our developments with the evolving EU Digital Product Passport standards, ensuring that the solutions remain robust, scalable, and future-ready.

References:

1. <https://aideas-project.eu>
2. <https://www.wood2wood-project.eu/>

Keywords: Digital Product Passport (DPP), Materials Informatics, FAIR Data, AI Models, Lifecycle Tracking, Sustainability Assessment, Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD), Materials Digitalization, Interoperability, EU Regulation, Standardization

ID: 403

Time: 15:10

Title: DigInTraCE: Novel transparent and interoperable Decentralised Traceability platform via the development of Dynamically updated Digital Product Passport schemes that support certification and quality validation in industrial set-ups

Project Reference: 101091801, Project Name: DigInTraCE, funded by the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)

Lefteris Gounaridis

Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) lefteris.gounaridis@iccs.gr

Abstract: As the transition to a circular and transparent economy accelerates, the Digital Product Passport (DPP) is emerging as a key enabler of data-driven sustainability. Serving as a standardized digital record, the DPP includes essential details on a product's composition, origin, environmental impact, repairability, and end-of-life options [1]. By making this data accessible across the value chain, it empowers stakeholders to support longer product lifespans, better resource recovery, and compliance with evolving EU regulations [2].

An important advancement of the DPP involves real-time tracking capabilities. By integrating RFID, and smart sensor, the DPP can evolve into a live digital twin of the product, enhancing traceability and offering insights into movement, handling, worker interaction, and operational anomalies [3][4].

To demonstrate this, we present a use case at an industrial facility in Koropi, Greece. A tracing system using RFID smart tags monitors each product from arrival to storage, capturing location data, staff interactions, and anomalies such as unauthorized movements. Alerts flag unusual patterns, like prolonged stays in restricted zones, while AI vision systems ensure fallback validation. Sorting results are also integrated into the DPP, creating a comprehensive and auditable digital footprint.

This case highlights how dynamic tracking strengthens the DPP's role as an intelligent tool for monitoring compliance, efficiency, and circularity metrics. It illustrates the broader potential of the next-generation DPPs to drive sustainable transformation across industrial ecosystems.

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2. Jensen, S.F. et al., 2023. "Digital product passports for a circular economy: Data needs for product life cycle decision-making." *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 37, pp.242–255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2023.02.021>
3. Demčák, J. et al., 2024. "Digital Twin for Monitoring the Experimental Assembly Process Using RFID." *Processes* 12, 1512. <https://doi.org/10.3390/pr12071512>
4. Ullah, A. et al., 2025. "Digital Twin Framework Using Real-Time Asset Tracking for Smart Flexible Manufacturing System." *Machines* 13, 37. <https://doi.org/10.3390/machines13010037>

Keywords: Digital Product Passport (DPP), Digital Twin, Real-Time Tracking, Circular Economy, Sustainability, RFID Technology, EU Regulation, Industry 4.0, Traceability, Smart Sensors

ID: 404**Time: 15:25**

Title: Development of the Digital Bio-product Passport for Environmental Impact Assessment in Bio-based Value Chains

Project Reference: Horizon Europe project ARGONAUT. Grant agreement ID: 101181978

Milenko Tasic

VizLore Labs Foundation milenko.tasic@vizlore.com

Abstract: The ARGONAUT project is developing a digital ecosystem to accurately assess the environmental impacts of bio-based products throughout their entire value chains. At its core, is JASON (Joint Analytical System for Optimization of environmental impact assessment), an AI-powered digital tool that employs sophisticated language models to analyze scientific technical data, applying Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methods to quantify a wide range of environmental impact categories.

Central to ARGONAUT's strategy is the Digital Bio-product Passport (DBP), a blockchain-enabled digital record and identity designed to securely document the key bio-based product's lifecycle data. The DBP provides immutable records and certified digital identities for bio-based products documenting their environmental impacts throughout the various life cycle stages, ensuring traceability, transparency, and interoperability across stakeholders. Using blockchain's smart contract capabilities, ARGONAUT ensures data integrity, privacy, and controlled access aligned with EU data strategies.

The integration of DBP within JASON significantly enhances the AI tool's decision-making capabilities by feeding standardized, verifiable lifecycle data directly into its analytics engine, ensuring high accuracy and reliability. Furthermore, ARGONAUT's DBP leverages emerging European federated data spaces, facilitating secure, scalable data sharing and interoperability among diverse actors in the bioeconomy.

The project solutions will be validated in 3 biomaterial/biochemical value chains (biopolymers, biomethane, nutraceutical), and 3 agro-food value chains (flour and byproducts, grass biorefinery and its byproducts, sauces and organic fertilisers from vegetables). On its way to achieve the set goals, the ARGONAUT project has initiated collaboration with the Horizon project SYMBA (MoU signed) and works towards close collaboration with the Horizon projects bi0space and 3CO.

Keywords: Digital Bio-product Passport (DBP), Environmental Impact Assessment, Bio-based Products, Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Blockchain, Data Interoperability, Data Traceability, EU Data Strategies, Digital Identity, Environmental Impact Categories, Data Sharing, Transparency

Session 5: Bridging Sustainable by Design (SSbD) Principles, Innovation and Manufacturing through DPPs.

Chairs: Natalia Konchakova, Peter Klein

This session examines the link between innovation processes and industrial manufacturing in implementing Digital Product Passports (DPPs). Building on previous discussions on Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD), the Circular Economy, and the technical requirements of DPPs, it will focus on the digitalization of SSbD principles and research-driven methodologies for seamless integration into industrial production and supply chains. This session will provide a comprehensive perspective on connecting research, policy, and industry, ensuring that DPPs are not just a regulatory tool but also a key enabler for sustainable innovation and circular economy transformation.

ID: 501

Title: Bridging the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) with Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD)

Time: 16:20

Project Reference: IRISS (101058245), EU*Lya G. Soeteman-Hernandez**National Institute for Public Health and the Environment lya.hernandez@rivm.nl*

Abstract: The Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) is a major European legislative initiative aimed at improving the environmental sustainability of products sold in the European Union (EU). The regulation is part of the European Green Deal and the Circular Economy Action Plan. The ESPR contributes to the objectives of EU industrial policy to boost the supply of and demand for sustainable goods, deliver on sustainable production, and ensure a level playing field for products sold on the internal market. Key Ecodesign product aspects include (a) product durability and reliability; (b) product reusability; (c) product upgradability, reparability, maintenance and refurbishment; (d) the presence of substances of concern in products; (e) product energy and resource efficiency; (f) recycled content in products; (g) product remanufacturing and recycling; (h) products' carbon and environmental footprints; (i) products' expected generation of waste materials.

Keywords: Safe and Sustainable by Design, DPP support, Recycling

From an innovation perspective, the European Commission's (EC) Joint Research Center (JRC) has developed a Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework and methodological guidance as a voluntary approach to guide the innovation process for chemicals, materials, products and manufacturing processes. SSbD aims to i) steer the innovation process towards the green and sustainable industrial transition, ii) minimise the production and use of substances of concern, in line with, and beyond existing and upcoming regulatory obligations, and iii) minimise the impact on health, climate and the environment during sourcing, production, use and end-of-life of chemicals, materials, products and manufacturing processes. The SSbD framework is composed of a (re-)design phase and an assessment phase that are applied iteratively as data becomes available. The (re-)design phase consists of the application of guiding principles to steer the development process. The goal, the scope and the system boundaries – which will frame the assessment of the chemical or material – are defined in this phase. The assessment phase comprises of hazard, workers exposure during production, exposure during use and life-cycle assessment. The assessment can be carried out either on newly developed chemicals and /or materials, or on existing chemicals and or materials to improve their safety and sustainability performance during production, use and /or end-of-life.

The alignment between the ESPR key Ecodesign aspects and the EC JRC SSbD framework and methodological guidance, as well as how to couple the innovation process seamlessly with the digital product passport (DPP), will be discussed. This can be done by for instance, feeding the SSbD assessment data into the DPP [e.g., Composition (incl. critical raw materials), Lifecycle data (CO₂, water, energy), Safety data (toxicology, exposure), Repair /disassembly instructions] and ensuring compatibility with upcoming EU DPP Delegated Acts (e.g., battery passport standards). In a feedback loop, the DPP can support not only traceability but also continuous improvement of product safety and sustainability.

ID: 502

Time: 16:35

Title: From conceptualizing a full material life cycle to a standards-based data model**Project Reference:** ABSolEU - 101058636; Funded by Horizon Europe under HORIZON.2.4 - Digital, Industry and Space, HORIZON.2.4.4 - Advanced Materials*Raul Carlsson**RISE Research Institutes of Sweden raul.carlsson@ri.se***Abstract:** This abstract presents the solution to ABS plastics circular traceability and material quality control developed in the ABSolEU-project, aiming to integrate with the European digital product passport (DPP). The objective is quality control of recycled and virgin plastic—from specification to use, EOL, and recycling. The approach enables full traceability of ABS plastic and its constituents, designed to be applicable to any material type.**Keywords:**

circular materials, data model, STEP standard, ISO 10303, material properties, material analysis, material processing, traceability, conceptual model, ABS, digital product passport

A principal approach to total material quality control was conceptualized, defining the two main necessary components and steps for data specification, acquisition, and exchange. Two main components were identified: (1) the combined physical and digital identification and traceability solution, and (2) the essential information needed for circular material traceability.

The traceability solution (1) aligns with the EU's DPP concept: each material sample receives a unique digital ID, either for a distinct material object or as a reference to a larger batch. Each object—e.g., a package of pellets or a single component—is physically marked, such as with a QR code, or identified by statistically significant property measurements enabling batch or category identification (outside the DPP scope).

To determine the essential information (2), a model was developed based on industry practices. It analyzed how companies secure material properties for products, beginning with specification of key properties—chemical, physical, mechanical—as well as quality indicators such as chemical purity and durability. These are typically defined via standardized analysis and test methods, implicitly requiring accredited laboratories. This is a central quality control aspect enabling trust in DPP data.

Additional essential information includes environmental exposure—such as production, logistics, temperature, and mechanical stress—throughout the product's life. This enables each material sample, batch, or component to carry data on optimal processing, use, sorting, EOL, and recycling, as well as its actual handling history. Such traceability is vital for circular material management and quality control, forming a kernel for a robust DPP. Associating material objects with their unique traceable data provides stakeholders with immediate insight into relevant material characteristics.

Building on this conceptualization, a logical model was developed, followed by a strict relational model, which was then mapped to ISO 10303 standard application protocols AP242 and AP235. This preserves the data model and ensures end-to-end traceability of both virgin and recycled materials. Based on the generalized conceptual model, this approach is extendable to any material or product category. AP242 is widely used in mechanical design (3D CAD) with embedded manufacturing data. The adoption of STEP standards enhances model robustness and compatibility across all product lifecycle phases: 'as designed', 'as manufactured', 'as tested', 'as recycled', 'as disposed', and 'as reused'.

Thus, the conceptual model for ABS plastics traceability and quality control developed in ABSolEU is generalized into a solution for circular traceability and material quality control, potentially serving as a compliant module within the European digital product passport framework.

ID: 503**Time: 16:50****Title:** Enabling Semantic Interoperability in Materials Science: The MaterialDigital Initiative**Project References:** 13XP5094A Bundesministerium Für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF) Germany*Jörg Schaarschmidt**Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) joerg.schaarschmidt@kit.edu*

Abstract: The unsustainable and conditionally reusable way of storing and handling data about materials has been identified by the materials science and engineering community as one of the major constraints for further qualitative growth in materials research and product design. The Initiative MaterialDigital was launched to enable and support a joint effort of MSE specialists from different materials domains and experts in semantic web technologies, scientific workflows and IT architecture to explore and find the best digitalisation approaches for materials data handling according to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles.

The MaterialDigital (PMD) platform aims to provide prototypical solutions for all the processes involved, including data acquisition, structuring, storage and processing. These different aspects are addressed within the platform's focus areas of IT architecture, semantic interoperability and workflows, and disseminated through the focus area community interaction working group.

Achieving semantic interoperability of material data across different material domains in an industrial data space is the fundamental goal of the initiative. The MaterialDigital projects cover a wide range of material domains in their research, from steel and copper to ceramics, semiconductors and rubber. This ensures that the digitalisation approaches developed in the platform can be applied to any MSE challenge. The platform also actively connects to other related national, European and international activities such as NFDI, Gaia-X or the DPP.

For more information about the MaterialDigital platform and the satellite projects, please visit our website: <http://material-digital.de>. For inquiries, contact us at info@material-digital.de.

Keywords: Materials Science, Semantic Interoperability, FAIR Principles, Data Management, Materials Data, IT Architecture, Digitalization, Materials Data Acquisition, Workflows, Industrial Data Space, Materials Domains, MSE Challenges, Data Structures, NFDI, Gaia-X, Digital Product Passport (DPP), Data Interoperability, Materials Engineering, Research Data, Sustainable Materials Data

ID: 504**Time: 17:05****Title:** Standardizing Composite Material Test Data for Digital Product Passports in Aerospace and Wind Energy Sectors**Project Reference:** D-STANDART, EU Horizon Europe Grant Agreement No. 101091409*Julian de Marchi**Royal Netherlands Aerospace Centre (NLR) julian.de.marchi@nlr.nl*

Abstract: As part of the D-STANDART project, we are gathering and processing raw data from hundreds of materials characterization simulations and tests for numerous variations in fibre-reinforced plastic composites. The results will be used to revise and recalibrate outdated models used to derive composite structure mechanical properties. Updating those models will allow us to more accurately predict the fatigue lifetimes of critical composite structures such as aerofoils used in wind turbines and jet engines.

Test datasets are generated and provided by- multiple partners, each using their own customary way-of-working. Collecting datasets in various formats, massaging them into a uniform, standardized format, and managing the data in a consistent, traceable fashion, has been a major project challenge. Additionally, we have made pertinent contributions to the CHADA v2 standard, and recently presented our data processing and management journey as part of the EMMC'25 conference.

Several challenges have included:

- Ensuring that metadata from different lab tests are recorded and preserved with uniform structure and quality;
- Making those metadata searchable in an effective, efficient, and useful way;
- Ensuring that source data can be consistently and reliably stored, discovered, accessed, and retrieved;
- Coupling materials characterization metadata into the EMMO ontology

In addition the DPP endeavours to include LCA data in order to aid reuse and recycling of composites.

¹Royal Netherlands Aerospace Centre (NLR)

Keywords: Composite Materials, Digital Product Passport (DPP), Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Aerospace, Wind Energy, Sustainability, Circular Economy, Data Standardization, Material Characterization, EMMO Ontology, EU Regulation

ID: 505**Title:** Digital Material and Product Passports: Advancing SSbD in the PINK Project**Time: 17:40****Project Reference:** PINK (Horizon Europe, Grant agreement No. 101137809)*Thomas Exner**Seven Past Nine thomas.exner@sevenpastnine.com*

Abstract: To achieve the goals of the European Green Deal and the new Clean Industrial Deal, advanced materials and chemicals are needed to provide new or improved functionalities and, at the same time, be both safe and sustainable. These materials need to be developed following the Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) paradigm. There is consensus that covering the demand across all material innovation markets is only possible by heavily relying on digital approaches for data collection, sharing, and gap filling. It is also essential that all stakeholders, starting with raw material providers, materials designers, integrators, distributors, waste managers, and recyclers, are integrated into the process of creating realistic views on material and product life cycles and complex, interlinked, and partly circular value chains. Additionally, all the required data must be collected for the holistic assessment needed for SSbD.

Keywords: Digital Product Passports, Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD), Interoperability Framework, Federated Data Systems, Circular Economy, Sustainable Innovation

The PINK project is currently designing and implementing major components for a technical and semantic Interoperability Framework to integrate data from all SSbD dimensions and stakeholders into a federated data system. These components are meant to be further generalized and made publicly available for adoption by other projects as part of a European digital material ecosystem. However, supporting all stakeholders is not only a question of data and tool availability. They also need to be interoperable and trustworthy. Data and tools from different providers must work together, and the results must be understandable and demonstrate accuracy and confidence to allow informed decisions. Digital material and product passports could play a key role here, as they could become a harmonized and trusted source for sharing SSbD data with clear provenance trails.

This presentation will elaborate on the benefits of integrating additional SSbD criteria in digital passports and utilizing these passports for data sharing along the value chain.

ID: 506**Time: 17:55****Title:** REMHub project: safe and sustainable REE by design framework**Project Reference:** REMHub, ID: 101177493, HORIZON-CL4-2024-RESILIENCE-01-08*Prof. Dr. Damijan Miljavec**University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Electrical Engineering damijan.miljavec@fe.uni-lj.si*

Abstract: The new Rare Earth and Magnets Hub for resilient Europe (REMHub) project creates a cutting-edge digital innovation hub propelling EU excellence for Rare Earth Elements (REEs) and permanent magnets. This is a four-year project funded under the Horizon EU call HORIZON-CL4-2024-RESILIENCE-01-08 which started in October 2024.

The project partners cover the entire REE value chain starting from mineral exploration, through mineral processing, recovering rare earths from side streams and refining to metal production and magnet making as well as recycling. The project incorporates a safe and sustainable by design framework including design for Re-X (recycling, reuse, refurbishment, repurposing, reduction of HREE and REE) approach integrating easy dismantling and circularity properties. The Re-X technologies for rare earths and valuable metals will be developed, along with electric machine designs that facilitate permanent magnet recycling.

The design framework towards digital passport formation will follow the development procedure by:

- Improving recyclability by design: The new electric machine design concept will follow the scalability and Design to Re-X aspects governed by digital twins, with minimal rare materials and high specific power density, allowing easy dismantling and using only a fraction of the energy currently needed for magnet extraction. For existing machines, energy-optimized dismantling processes will be developed.
- Geo-based traceability: Primary REE production chains will utilize geochemical and isotopic signatures to track raw material origin and associated sustainability data. A coding system will make this info accessible across the supply chain.
- Digital twinning and digital passport: an over-the-life cycle digitalised REE closed chain will be introduced, from different material sourcing via novel production process to guarantee optimal choices in different phases of the REE cycle. The digital twins will enable reducing and optimising the overall energy usage as well as to minimise the emission pollution. Permanent magnet (PM) digital passport in form of QR code will contain properties and chemical composition (list and amount of REE material inside the magnets) with their dismantling procedure, realising all aspects of Re-X approach after magnets' end-of-life. By introducing the permanent magnet digital passport, we are introducing safe and sustainable usage of chemicals and materials from the early stages of innovation and along their entire life cycle

This approach introduces a safe and sustainable usage framework for chemicals and materials throughout their entire life cycle.

Keywords: Rare Earth Elements (REEs), Permanent Magnets (PMs), Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD), Digital Product Passport (DPP), Circular Economy, Re-X Technologies

Session 6: Enabling industrial and manufacturing data ecosystems.

Chairs: Kostas Chatziioannou, Stella Georgali

Experts will discuss how manufacturing process data can be used to enhance DPPs and inversely, including business-to-business (B2B) and business-to-research (B2RTO) data sharing, data privacy concerns, federated data spaces, and conditions for secure reuse of sensitive industrial data. Topics will also include the challenges and opportunities in data access control, data updates, as well as usage and availability limitations. The role of DPPs in process industries, in manufacturing set-ups, industrial symbiosis, Hubs for Circularity (H4C) or Circular Cities & Regions will be explored. The session will also address innovations in data spaces for industry, such as federated and local data spaces, platforms that support data access and interoperability among European Data Spaces, and the role that emerging technologies can play in contributing to this.

ID: 601

Title: SMARTChain: Digital Material and Product Passports driving circularity, innovation, and quality in the steel supply chain

Time: 09:20

Project Reference: 101178919, Project Name: SMARTChain, funded by the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA)

Stella Georgali

Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) stella.georgali@iccs.gr

Abstract: The steel industry is at a critical turning point, with digitalization playing a key role in driving sustainability, transparency, and circularity [1]. Digital Product Passports (DPPs) are emerging as a foundational tool to support this transformation by providing accessible, structured, and dynamic product information throughout a product's lifecycle.

Keywords: Steel Industry, Digital Product Passport (DPP), Circular Economy, Transparency, Sustainability, Ecodesign Regulation, Industrial Data Space, EU Regulation

SMARTChain, an EU-funded Horizon Europe project, is developing and piloting dynamic DPPs in collaboration with industrial actors across the steel, automotive, consumer goods, and machinery sectors. These passports enable end-to-end traceability, improved product quality, and more sustainable decision-making, aligning with upcoming requirements from regulatory frameworks such as the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation [2]. The project also focuses on building an Industrial Data Space to ensure secure and interoperable data exchange across the value chain—from steelmakers to steel users.

Pilot activities are being carried out with a group of high-profile industrial partners, to test DPP solutions in real operational environments. These pilots demonstrate how data on material properties, production processes, and environmental performance can drive circularity, improve collaboration, and unlock new value for both manufacturers and end-users.

This work will explore the enabling role of interoperable digital infrastructure and highlight how DPPs can lay the groundwork for a more circular, transparent, and data-informed industrial future.

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101178919 (SMARTChain).

References:

1. Clean Steel Partnership (CSP), 2021. Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). https://www.estep.eu/assets/CSP/CSP_SRIA_Oct2021_clean.pdf
2. European Commission, 2024. Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L.202401781>

ID: 602**Time: 09:35****Title:** DigiPass CSA: Coordinating the European DPP Ecosystem**Project Reference:** DigiPass CSA (Coordination and Support Action)*Salim Belouettar**Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST) salim.belouettar@gmail.com*

Abstract: The DigiPass CSA serves as a strategic enabler for aligning and accelerating Digital Product Passport (DPP) implementation across European sectors. As a Coordination and Support Action, the initiative focuses on mapping the evolving DPP landscape, fostering collaboration among stakeholders, and harmonizing frameworks for interoperability, standardization, and data governance.

With active participation from national and EU-level initiatives, DigiPass CSA aims to:

- Support the operationalization of the ESPR through actionable roadmaps and knowledge sharing;
- Facilitate convergence across pilot projects and technical working groups;
- Provide input into ongoing regulatory, technological, and standardization efforts;
- Build a cohesive community of practice to ensure scalable and trustworthy DPP adoption.

By integrating expertise from across the ecosystem—including research institutes, regulators, industry, and technology developers—the CSA strengthens the foundations for cross-sectoral data interoperability and governance frameworks. LIST's contribution focuses on establishing a sustainable, science-based architecture for future DPP deployment, ensuring that environmental and circularity goals are met through rigorous, coordinated action.

Keywords: Digital Product Passports (DPP), European DPP Ecosystem, Coordination and Support Action (CSA), ESPR, Interoperability, Data Governance, Standardization, Circular Economy, Pilot Projects, Regulatory Efforts, Technology Development, Cross-sector Collaboration, Community of Practice, Sustainability

ID: 603**Time: 09:50**

Title: The Digital Product Information Systems (DPIS) Global Framework: Harmonizing Sustainability Data for a Global Impact

Project References: Multiple UNEP grants and funds from EU member states. For example, eco-advance from the German Federal Ministry for the Environment.

Ana Gabriela Vergara

United Nations Environment Programme ana.fernandezvergara@un.org

Abstract: The Digital Product Information Systems (DPIS) Global Framework represents an overarching vision to harmonize product sustainability data systems globally. It sets out the guidelines and principles that will steer the development, implementation, and harmonization of DPIS across diverse industries and regions.

Key objectives of the framework include achieving global consensus on the data categories of DPIS, promoting the adoption of high-level principles on data governance and technology architecture aligned with the Global Environmental Data Strategy. It champions the sustainability priorities of the Global South, ensuring that DPIS are designed to serve environmental and development goals equitably across all regions. The framework also recommends the adoption of financial mechanisms and capacity-building strategies for the implementation of DPIS, ensuring that these systems benefit all countries without creating trade barriers.

Core principles guiding the framework include inclusion and stakeholder centrality, which prioritize regional adaptability and accessibility, particularly for SMEs and actors in the Global South. The framework also promotes interoperability across diverse systems without mandating specific technologies. With a sector-agnostic approach, it ensures applicability across industries and facilitates the smooth exchange of sustainability data worldwide. Through systems thinking, it acknowledges the complexities of global value chains and emphasizes the interconnectedness of stakeholders, regions, and data flows.

Adopting this framework will reduce trade barriers, increase inclusivity, enhance efficiency, and improve scalability. It minimizes redundancy in data exchange, harmonizes efforts across regions, and fosters transparent value chains, ultimately contributing to the widespread adoption of sustainable practices and advancing global sustainability goals.

Keywords: Digital Product Information Systems (DPIS), Sustainability Data, Global Framework, Global South, Data Governance, Technology Architecture, Interoperability, Inclusivity, Stakeholder-Centric, SMEs, Environmental Data Strategy, Global Value Chains, Sustainability, Trade Barriers, Capacity-Building, Regional Adaptability, Global Consensus, Data Exchange, Harmonization, Financial Mechanisms

ID: 604**Title:** AI-driven Decision Making in Material Selection for Sustainability using Digital Product Passports**Time: 10:05****Project Reference:** MOZART*Maddalena Rostagno**DG Advanced m.rostagno@dg-advanced.com***Abstract:**

In the manufacturing sector, material selection, particularly for surface treatments, remains largely experience-driven, often disconnected from objective environmental criteria. This work explores a transformative approach where the Digital Product Passport (DPP) becomes a central enabler for sustainability-aware decision making. By acquiring Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) data directly from the DPP and applying AI-driven clusterization techniques, we demonstrate how material choice could evolve into a traceable, intelligent, and impact-informed process.

Focusing on harmful coatings, LCI data were extracted and cleaned to ensure consistency and high quality across key environmental indicators calculated with a LLM model: Climate Change, Human Toxicity, Particulate Matter, Water Depletion, and Fossil Depletion. Dimensionality reduction via Principal Component Analysis (PCA) enabled interpretation of the most relevant impact drivers, while K-means clustering revealed distinct environmental profiles among coating processes.

The results show significant variability in performance across different surface treatment processes. Some exhibit high toxicity and particulate emissions, highlighting the need for prioritization in substitution strategies. Others demonstrate consistently low impacts, positioning them as strong candidates for sustainable design choices in manufacturing components.

By embedding AI-powered analytics into the material selection workflow and sourcing data from the DPP, this work lays the foundation for a more transparent, efficient, and environmentally responsible manufacturing industry.

Keywords: AI-driven Decision Making, Material Selection, Digital Product Passports (DPP), Sustainability, Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), Surface Treatments, Environmental Impact, AI Analytics, Environmental Profiles, Sustainable Manufacturing

ID: 605**Time: 10:40****Title:** How to Create, Exchange, and Use DPPs in Industrial & Manufacturing Data Ecosystems**Project References:** FACTORY-X, NextGenerationEU, Grant No. 13MX001 Funding Agency: BMWK (German Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Climate Action)*Christoph Attila Kun**BASF christoph-attila.kun@basf.com*

Abstract: Industrial production of goods is the core of prosperous economies. In Europe, approximately 20% of all jobs depend on the manufacturing industry, and production facilities are the heart of it.

The factory equipment plays an important role for sustainable production as it directly influences energy and manufacturing process efficiency, repairability & upgradability of the production facilities, extending their useful life. All of this has an impact on sustainability of production processes and the competitiveness of Europe as production location. To increase sustainability and competitiveness factory equipment manufacturer must make their product information available as DPP and exchange it in a data ecosystem with all stakeholders.

The Factory-X project (FX) aims to develop technologies necessary to enable data ecosystems, with its DPP exchange and management mechanisms. FX outlines how DPPs are a key enabler of data ecosystems:

- Cross sectoral system & semantical interoperability is the basis for a data ecosystem. FX aims to align & develop components necessary to enable an industrial & manufacturing data ecosystem
- The data ecosystem architecture must be suitable for SMEs as well as corporations. The FX partner ecosystem covers all sizes of companies, to ensure that all partners are able to join the data ecosystem
- FX aims to integrate manufacturing process data like CO2 emission, use of water, generation of waste into the DPP
- The presentation illustrates the groundbreaking role of DPPs for data exchange and provide an overview of DPP use cases in industry.

To create a data ecosystem collaboration between all relevant sectors is crucial. By joining all forces and harmonizing technologies, we will be able to build the sustainable circular economy as new foundation for Europe's competitiveness. We invite all sectors, experts and researchers to join forces with FX to reach this goal together

Keywords: Digital Product Passport (DPP), Industrial Data Ecosystems, Sustainability, Manufacturing, Energy Efficiency, Repairability, Upgradability, CO2 Emissions, Water Usage, Waste Generation, Cross-Sectoral Interoperability, Circular Economy, Manufacturing Competitiveness, EU Regulation, FACTORY-X

ID: 606**Time: 10:55**

Title: Digital Product Passports and Circular Manufacturing Data Spaces: Two Sides of the Same Twin Transition Coin

Project Reference: Circular TwAIn, Horizon Europe Grant Agreement 101058585; HADEA; ADRA and MADE in EUROPE partnerships

Cinzia Rubattino

*ENGINEERING Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A. cinzia.rubattino@eng.it ;
sergio.gusmeroli@polimi.it*

Abstract: Digital Product Passports (DPP) are one of the most disruptive innovations that in the near future will affect many strategic EU Manufacturing sectors driving them towards a Circular Economy perspective and a more responsible twin transition.

The aim of the Circular TwAIn HEP proposed submission is to demonstrate that regarding Session 6 focus “Enabling Industrial and manufacturing data ecosystems” the advent of DPPs represents an evolution (and not a radical greenfield revolution) in the B2G and B2C direction of existing well developed B2B Circular Data Spaces developed in the recent years along the Manufacturing value chains. The project in fact integrates Data Spaces and AI-based Digital twins (of product/materials, of manufacturing and re-manufacturing processes, of Engineers and Human Operators), towards a more circular and environmentally responsible EU Manufacturing Industry. Three industrial cases are being developed in the re-manufacturing of EV Batteries, of WEEE and in the waste reduction of Petro-chemical industry. We wish to underline and discuss the following aspects:

- Data exchange systems do exist in Manufacturing since 20+ years now (e.g. EDI)
- In recent years, they became open, interoperable and standard Data Spaces (IDSA, DSSC, RAMI4.0, Asset Administration Shell)
- More recently, the need to develop non-hierarchical cross-sector value networks and to embrace circular economy principles has led to the creation of Manufacturing Data Spaces for Circular Economy DPPs are intimately linked to this evolution of CE Manufacturing Data Spaces and represent an unprecedented business opportunity and not just a regulatory obligation for those manufacturers which already put in place collaboration and data exchange mechanisms for the circular value chain.

This is the thesis of the Circular TwAIn proposed submission: DPPs and CE Data Spaces are the two sides of the same Twin Transition coin and need to proceed hand-to-hand in the development and industrial experimentation of relevant Data Ecosystems.

Keywords: Circular Data Spaces, Twin Transition, AI-enhanced Digital Twins, EV Battery Re-manufacturing, WEEE Management, Petro-chemical Waste Reduction, Interoperable Data Infrastructures, Asset Administration Shell, Sustainability, Cross-sector Value Networks

ID: 607**Title:** SENECA: Advancing Sustainability through Digital Product Passports and Data Spaces**Time: 11:10****Project References:** EXP 00154828 / MIG-20221047 - CDTI (Spain)*Carlos Méndez**Capgemini carlos.a.mendez@capgemini.com*

Abstract: SENECA is a R&D project where 9 entities are participating in order to advance in three different sustainability areas: A) Critical Material (Ti, Co, Li, Cr, Ni, Mn, W, V) recovery processes; B) Product manufacturing with Secondary Raw Materials (SRW) C) Traceability of the composition of these products through a DPP deployed on a Data Space. SENECA started in 2023 and will finish in June 2025. One of the results achieved is the development and testing of a Digital Product and Materials Passport platform, developed by Capgemini and supported by Tekniker.

On the one hand, it incorporates lifecycle information to enhance traceability & transparency into supply especially around sustainability metrics such as environmental footprint and circularity. It aligns with the UNECE's DPP data model (UNTP B2B DPP Vocabulary) and includes lifecycle information from SENECA's own revalorization processes, such as the extraction and valorization of scrap metals from cutting processes, the use of different mechanical and chemical processes (eg. Membranes, ionic liquids ...) to separate metals, or the synthesis or new elements (i.e. electrolytes).

On the other hand, the platform is ready to operate as part of a Data Space Ecosystem allowing a trusted data sharing in the value chain through the implementation of Eclipse Data Connector and an identity management that is compliant with both IDSA (and the Data Space Protocol) and GAIA-X. Moreover, SENECA's architecture incorporates semantic models that facilitate interoperability between industrial sectors, federation and decentralization capabilities, and automated federated governance supported by federated catalogs (DCAT) and access policies defined through OLDR that guarantee the sovereignty of owners over the data they provide to the DPP.

As a result SENECA provides a viable platform to support the traceability of SRW across European industries, and may also impact on the optimization of their extraction and valorization processes

Keywords: Digital Product Passport (DPP), Data Space, Circular Economy, Sustainability, Critical Material Recovery, Secondary Raw Materials (SRW), Lifecycle Information, Traceability, Environmental Footprint, Circularity, UNECE Data Model, Data Sharing, Interoperability, Federation, Decentralization, Data Sovereignty, IDSA, GAIA-X, Federated Governance

ID: 608**Time: 11:25****Title:** PASSAT - Product Access and Secure Sharing by Automated Trust**Project Reference:** PASSAT*Rigo Wenning**RRW rigo@wenning.org*

Abstract: The Digital Product Passport(DPP) is at a cross-roads. If the DPP only contains information as mandated by law, it will be mostly a bureaucratic exercise with limited use for a circular economy. Talking to industry, one of the core concerns with respect to DPP information, beyond what is mandated, is that data could be abused for purposes other than recycling.

Keywords: Digital Product Passport (DPP), Usage Control, Access Control, Information Governance, Circular Economy

A first reflex invokes access control as a remedy. Only select people will have access to information seen as touching on commercial secrets. Yet, recycling is a market and also an industry with division of labour. A centralized classic access control has several limitations. It requires a centralized identity management and puts all the burden on the manufacturer. As the concern is about the abuse of information, this needs to be included, but classic access control cannot transport that information. This generates a feeling of all-or-nothing access. This in turn is a great incentive not to share anything unless complex legal contract-work has been done.

To that challenge, industry responded with new models for fine grained access control and a complex protocol standardised in XACML that knows about Policy Decision Points and Policy Enforcement Points. This allows for role-based access (I'm a recycler), but isn't addressing the limitations beyond mere access. It also requires a rather rigid system architecture that may interfere with business models.

To address limitations, constraints and obligations of a party accessing information, academia responded with the invention of usage control. Usage control needs to be distinguished from Digital Rights Management(DRM) that has an enforcement point inside the systems of the information receiver. DRM is impossible to implement at the scale of the circular economy. But usage control scales very well. It first labels information with constraints and obligations. This way, those constraints can be automatically followed and abuse is very easy to assess. It scales well as information can not only be found, it also remembers its own constraints. This way, systems can have industrialised automatic compliance evidence that can be controlled periodically or on demand without effort. The submission will explain that technology.

ID: 609**Time: 11:40****Title:** What does a chemical DPP contribute to building a sustainable circular economy?**Project Reference:** Chem-X: FKZ 13MX010A, funded by BMWK (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz) in collaboration with the EU (Next Generation EU)*Adrian von Muehlenen**BASF SE adrian.a.von-muehlenen@basf.com***Abstract:** The chemical industry is vital for the green transition, with chemicals present in 96% of European products. Moreover, chemical processes are essential for recycling materials. The Chem-X team suggests Digital Product Passports (DPPs) to manage material flows and ensure information interoperability throughout their lifecycle.**Interoperability:** Seamless integration and harmonization of data across sectors are vital. The Chem-X project aims to align technical interfaces and harmonize information models.**Collaboration:** Collaboration is essential to align interfaces with other sectors. The Chem-X project will be the catalyst for interoperability between sector-specific DPP initiatives.**Pilot Projects:** Pilot projects will demonstrate data transfers along the supply chains as well as the viability of recycling concepts by re-inserting materials at various levels of the value chain. Examples from the textile industry, tires, and batteries showcase the potential of these initiatives.**Economic Competitiveness:** Economic competitiveness can be achieved through recycled products, and adequate value chains have to be designed. Information about material composition is key to optimizing reverse logistics and sorting.**Presentation:** The presentation will illustrate the crucial role of DPP in real-world applications and offer an outlook on how results of Chem-X and demonstrators will validate the concept.**Request for Action:** We invite all stakeholders to collaborate with the Chem-X project. Close collaboration can ensure that interfaces are aligned, and data requirements are harmonized across sectors.**Conclusion:** The successful implementation of a circular economy enabled by DPPs will require a concerted effort from all sectors. By achieving technical and content interoperability through harmonization and collaboration, we can build a sustainable circular economy that benefits everyone.**Keywords:** Chemical Industry, Digital Product Passport (DPP), Circular Economy, Recycling, Interoperability, EU Regulation, Sustainability, Cross-Sector Collaboration
¹Chem-X / BASF SE

Session 7: From research to commercial valorization.

Chairs: Franz Pirker, Stella Georgali

This session will explore the business potential of DPPs, focusing on their value in digital platforms, open innovation strategies, and sustainable business models across multiple industries. The EU 27 contributes only 4 percentage of global capital investment in the digital economy, in strong contrast to the United States' 74 percentage, dominated by major players like Google, Apple, etc. This disparity reflects Europe's untapped potential, stemming largely from widespread misconceptions about digitalisation. Digitalisation extends far beyond data spaces, software development, ontologies, or digital twins; it is fundamentally about leveraging digital technologies to redefine business models, unlock new revenue streams, and create value. According to Gartner, "Digitalisation is the use of digital technologies to change a business model and provide new revenue and value-producing opportunities; it is the process of moving to a digital business."

ID: 701

Title: A large scale DPP initiative in France and in Europe

Time: 13:20

Project Reference: A collaboration between the CE-RISE and CircThread projects

[Xavier Lantoinette](#)

[WEEE Forum a.i.s.b.l.](#) xlantoinette@ecosystem.eco

Abstract: This pilot is led by Ecosystem, a French Producer Responsibility Organization (PRO), with support from the WEEE Forum and the Circular Intelligence Association. It involves manufacturers, retailers, and repairers, with the goal of tracing approximately two million appliances over a two-year period, tracking their lifecycle stages from manufacturing to reuse, repair, and recycling.

Keywords: Data Governance, Transparency, Traceability, Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), Collective Deployment, Consumer Trust, Refurbished Products, Non-Proprietary Blockchain, Pilot Initiative

Key aspects of the project include:

- Openness to all stakeholders, including manufacturers, retailers, repairers, and recyclers, ensuring broad participation.
- Rapid pilot launch with a limited number of initial stakeholders and gradual expansion.
- The use of non-proprietary blockchain technology to facilitate data sharing and governance among participants.
- A dedicated working group responsible for the governance of the data and platform.

The pilot will track the environmental performance of the solution by evaluating the avoided impacts of extending the product lifespan through repair, reuse, and remanufacture. The project began in October 2024, and the first DPPs were created just a few weeks ago. Initial participating companies include BEKO (Producer), DARTY (Retailer, Producer, and Re-pairer), and ENVIE (Repairer, Reuse, and Remanufacturer). GS1 France is also involved, with discussions underway to bring in more producers and retailers. The initiative aligns with the EU's Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR) and seeks to demonstrate the value of collective deployment in scaling DPPs across the sector. Through this initiative, the project will contribute to the transparency, traceability, and circularity of products, fostering greater consumer trust in refurbished and reused products.

ID: 702**Title:** TRACE4EU – Digital Product Passports Leveraging the European Blockchain Service Infrastructure**Time: 13:35****Project Reference:** GAP-101102743, European Commission[Steffen Schwalm](#)[msg systems ag](#) steffen.schwalm@msg.group

Abstract: TRACE4EU is a project co-funded by the European Commission under the Digital Europe Programme with \approx 30 partners. It's lead by Intesi group and msg. TRACE4EU designs and implement use cases on product- and material traceability with clear focus on digital product passport using the European Blockchain Service Infrastructure (EBSI) and so strength European Digital Sovereignty.

Keywords: European Blockchain Service Infrastructure (EBSI), Material Traceability, Supply Chains, EUDI Wallets, eIDAS 2.0, Qualified Attestations, European Standardization, Blockchain, Interoperability, Trusted Data Exchange, EU Regulation, Digital Identity

Technically TRACE4EU is based on EBSI and adds a Traceability Toolbox developed in the project as building block for European Companies and authorities. Practically we combine organizational wallets and identities concerning the new eIDAS Regulation with (qualified) attestation of attributes representing the DPP and the evidence for the supply chain (Traceability). The use case is e.g. Digital product Passport for batteries acc. to EU regulation. Means, every part of the product developed within the product life-cycle is made evident with single attestation of attributes issued by certain producer (or independent trust service) into the related wallet - the whole DPP is created within the supply chain - so that the one for full product contains the evidences for each component as a container which represents the DPP.

Additionally to fulfil also the requirements on EU Regulation on Supply Chain TRACE4EU ensures that each step in the supply chain is track and traced as traceability event in EBSI and linked to the corresponding evidence (Attestations). Means the DPP makes also the supply chain evident to 3rd parties as each event can contain qualified timestamp and/or qualified seal acc. to eIDAS.

With this combination of components coming from eIDAS so combination of digital identities, attestations and transactions using EBSI, the TRACE4EU project shows how the use of European Infrastructures with governmental trust anchor (as EBSI provided by EU member states), wallets and trust services shape core initiatives and regulations in the EU and strength European Digital Sovereignty.

We aim to present the approach, challenges and solutions to the audience. This also includes how results from TRACE4EU are contributed to European & international standardization on DPP and eIDAS in CEN JTC 24, CEN JTC 19, ETSI and ISO to ensure international interoperability and provability.

ID: 703**Time: 13:50****Title:** Proposal for a Cross-Project Working Group on DPP Use Cases in Electronics**Project Reference:** Project PACE-DPP; Funding Agency: FFG (Austria), <https://dpp-austria.at/>*Bernhard Bergmair**Silicon Austria Labs GmbH bernhard.bergmair@silicon-austria.com*

Abstract: Although the research project PACE-DPP (nationally funded by Austria) has only recently begun, initial discussions have already highlighted fundamental questions regarding the identification and evaluation of Digital Product Passport (DPP)-enabled circular use cases in the electronics sector. In light of this, we propose the establishment of a cross-project working group to explore these questions collaboratively across EU- and nationally funded initiatives.

Keywords: Digital Product Passport (DPP), Circular Economy, Electronics Sector, Sustainable Product Design, Policy Recommendations

The working group would aim to develop a common understanding of high-impact circular strategies supported by DPPs in electronics, addressing challenges such as the trade-off between product durability and technological upgrade cycles, as well as the environmental footprint of components versus entire systems. A further objective would be the development of a simplified assessment approach to identify and prioritize promising use cases.

Based on these insights, the group would also work towards policy recommendations concerning the data requirements of the DPP and additional regulatory needs, such as performance standards and liability considerations. The proposed working group seeks to create synergies across research efforts and contribute to the strategic alignment of DPP implementation with circular economy objectives.

ID: 704**Title:** Business Models across Safe and Sustainable by Design-, Open Innovation Test Beds and Digital Materials and Product Passport initiatives**Time: 14:05****Project Reference:** DigiPass CSA

Franz Pirker

AC2T research GmbH franz.pirker@ac2t.at

Abstract: Under the Horizon Europe Work Programme, the European Commission has launched strategic calls and initiatives to advance the European Green Deal and the Circular Economy Action Plan. These initiatives fund projects focused on sustainable innovation across various stages of development:

Keywords: Digital Business Models, Digital Materials and Product Passport, Safe and Sustainable by Design, Open Innovation Test Beds.

- Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD): Projects aimed at developing safer and more sustainable chemicals, materials, products, and processes from the outset of innovation.
- Open Innovation Test Beds (OITBs): Collaborative platforms and consortia that support the testing and validation of materials and products at different Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs).
- Digital Product Passports (DPP): Projects accelerating the deployment of DPPs across industrial sectors, with the concept of DPP as a Service to enhance traceability and sustainability.

All projects are designed with long-term sustainability in mind, aiming to establish a self-sustaining ecosystem for the exploitation of their key outcomes. This presentation will explore the various business models developed within these projects and examine potential synergies and interconnections among them.

Acknowledgement: **DigiPass CSA**, HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-39, GA No. 101138510. WIKKI LIMITED, UK participant in Horizon Europe Project DigiPass, is supported by UKRI grant number 10100819. Title: Harmonization of Advanced Materials Ecosystems serving strategic Innovation Markets to pave the way to a Digital Materials & Product Passport. <https://ms.hereon.de/digipass/index.php.en>

SiToLub, HORIZON-CL4-2023-RESILIENCE-01-23, GA No. 101138807, Title: Simulation Tools For The Design Of Safe And Sustainable Lubricants. <https://sitolub.eu/>

i-TRIBOMAT OITB, H2020-NMBP-TO-IND-2018-2020, GA No. 814494, Title: Intelligent Open Test Bed for Materials Tribological Characterisation Services. <https://i-tribomat.eu/>

Final Session: Panel Discussion on the Future of DPPs.

Chair: Natalia Konchakova

As the DPP4EU conference concludes, this high-level panel discussion will bring together leading experts, policymakers, and industry pioneers to explore the future of Digital Product Passports (DPPs) and their transformative role in shaping Europe's digital and circular economy. This session will go beyond technical insights, offering strategic perspectives on how DPPs can drive sustainable innovation, regulatory compliance, and global competitiveness.

Panelists will address critical **open questions**, including:

- How will DPPs evolve beyond compliance to become a business enabler?
- What are the next policy and standardisation steps for DPP adoption across industries and the EU value chain?
- How can emerging technologies like AI and IoT enhance DPP functionality?
- Which effort & actions towards different communities will you provide to support the DPPs implementation and adoption?
- How can we make best use of the knowledge in this community and create synergies?
- Who will control data?

Panelists:

- Eva-Kathrin Schillinger (IAM-I)
- Fani Tsiantonaki (HaDEA)
- Thomas Ebert (DG CONNECT, European Commission)
- Martin Policar (DG RTD, European Commission)
- Eugenio Alessandro Canepa (Piacenza 1733, TRICK Project)
- Peter Klein (Fraunhofer ITWM, DigiPass CSA Project)

Open Microphone Session: Future collaboration discussion.

Chair: Carollynn Bernier

The session provides a forum to discuss opportunities and ideas for the future collaboration between DPP-, digitalisation-, SSbD- and materials modeling related projects and EU- / national initiatives. In-person participants wishing to share their ideas for collaboration have the possibility to sign up with the chair of the open microphone session in order to provide a short pitch to the community.